

Nanoscopic structure of ionic liquids by neutron and X-ray diffraction^ψ

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Ionic liquids, consisting solely of ions, encompass both the classical high-temperature (HTMS) and the new and fast emerging room-temperature (RTMS) molten salts. They are used as electrolytes in energy technology field for energy storage and generation. They have physical properties closely related to their nano-scale (1 nm = 10 Å) structure, which can be probed experimentally by neutron (ND) and X-ray (XRD) diffraction techniques.

A vast amount of structural work by employing these techniques on a variety of HTMS, except molten fluorides, has been reported in literature over the past several decades. The RTMS are currently attracting great interest as "green solvents" for catalysis and low temperature synthetic chemical purposes. Although numerous studies concerning their preparation, physical and electrochemical properties, and their use as a reaction medium have been reported, little is known about their liquid structure. A wide variation in their properties can be obtained by changing the alkyl chain on the cation or the anion. But, the complex nature of these very ions makes the structural elucidation of the RTMS a difficult task. Despite this, some structural work on these liquids by complementary use of experimental and modelling techniques is just beginning to appear.

Similarly, molten fluorides belonging to the high-temperature class of ionic liquids are although technologically the most important, but the least investigated systems so far. This has been due, in principal, to the technical difficulties encountered under high operating temperatures and the associated corrosion and containment problems. More background work to solve these technical problems for ND and XRD work is required before these studies can be undertaken. Much international effort is being focussed recently to overcome these difficul-

ties, and new structural work on molten fluorides by using X-ray absorption fine structure (XAFS) is beginning to appear. In this article, we shall first introduce the neutron and X-ray techniques as structural probes, before discussing their applications to a wide range of ionic liquids.

1. Neutron and X-ray techniques

Although X-rays and neutrons have been used to investigate liquid structure for over fifty years, it is really only since the mid 1970's that methods became sufficiently robust to obtain detailed interatomic structure in ionic liquids. Foremost amongst these methods is that of Neutron Diffraction and Isotopic Substitution (NDIS)¹, where combinations of differences between the scattering patterns of isotopically labelled samples can be used to obtain information directly on the pair-wise structure. In the same period, second generation X-ray synchrotron sources enabled the application of EXAFS (extended X-ray absorption fine structure) spectroscopy and AXD (anomalous X-ray diffraction) as viable methods to probe the local structure around relatively heavy atoms (ions) in condensed phases². EXAFS and AXD exploit the high X-ray flux and the wide range of wavelengths available on synchrotrons. These are now commonly used to investigate structure specific to atoms with atomic numbers greater than 28. More recently, with the construction of third generation X-ray synchrotron sources in the 1990's, both techniques have been further improved to enable the structure determination of complex ionic liquids under a variety of states and conditions even more accurately.

X-Rays and neutrons have their distinct advantages and disadvantages (Table 1) in determining the structure of ionic liquids. A particular choice is made depending on the system and information required.

^ψDedicated to Professor H. C. Gaur on his 80th birthday.

Table 1. Advantages and disadvantages of X-ray and neutron scattering methods

	Advantages	Disadvantages
X-Rays	High fluxes Scattering proportional to atomic number Single sample	Strong container scattering Convolution of structure due to Q -dependent form factor Scattering anisotropic
Neutrons	Availability of isotopes Formal link to pair-wise structure Scattering isotropic Can easily identify hydrogen	Relatively low fluxes Several identical samples Expense and non-availability of isotopes

Table 2. Neutron scattering lengths³ of some chosen elements and their isotopes

Element	b_c^*/fm
natH, ² H (D)	-3.7390 (11), 6.671 (4)
natLi, ⁶ Li, ⁷ Li	-1.90 (2), 2.00 (11), -2.22 (2)
natN, ¹⁵ N	9.36 (2), 6.44 (3)
natCl, ³⁵ Cl, ³⁷ Cl	9.5770 (8), 11.65 (2), 3.08 (6)
natNi, ⁶² Ni	10.3 (1), -8.7 (2)
natDy, ¹⁶² Dy	16.9 (2), -1.4 (5)

*Bound coherent scattering length.

The main advantage of neutron methods rests on the fact that neutrons interact predominantly with atomic nuclei through the strong force and the interaction is isotropic. As a result structural information in the form of pair distribution functions (PDFs), $g_{\alpha\beta}(r)$'s, is accessible directly from the experimental diffraction data. Moreover, the strength of interaction characterized by the parameter b_α (the scattering length³) varies from isotope to isotope (see Table 2).

Thus, two ionic liquids with the same composition of atomic material but containing isotopically different nuclei (e.g. ³⁵Cl for ³⁷Cl, ⁶²Ni for natNi, H for D, etc.) will give different neutron scattering patterns. This enables detailed information, which is specific to the isotopically substituted species, to be obtained⁴⁻⁸. The main advantage of X-ray methods is the availability of large fluxes, as much as 10⁵ times greater than those available in equivalent neutron experiments. These can be used for faster data acquisition.

The formalism for both the structural probes begins with the same initial equation which gives the intensity, $I(Q)$, of the scattered neutrons or X-rays as,

$$I(Q) = \sum_{\alpha} \sum_{\beta} b_{\alpha} b_{\beta} \left\langle \sum_{i(\alpha)} \sum_{j(\beta)} \exp iQ \cdot (r_j(\beta) - r_i(\alpha)) \right\rangle$$

$$= N \left[\sum_{\alpha} c_{\alpha} b_{\alpha}^2 + \sum_{\alpha} \sum_{\beta} c_{\alpha} c_{\beta} b_{\alpha} b_{\beta} [S_{\alpha\beta}(Q) - 1] \right], \quad (1)$$

where $c_{\alpha} = N_{\alpha}/N$, $r_i(\alpha)$ denotes the position of the i -th nucleus of α -type characterised by a neutron scattering length or X-ray form factor, b_{α} , and Q is the scattering vector whose modulus, Q , for elastic scattering (i.e. for $|k_0| = |k_1| = 2\pi/\lambda$), is given by

$$Q = |Q| = 4\pi \sin \theta/\lambda. \quad (2)$$

θ is half the scattering angle, and λ is the wavelength of the incident neutrons or X-rays. The angular brackets indicate that an ensemble average has been taken, and $S_{\alpha\beta}(Q)$ are the partial structure factors. Each $S_{\alpha\beta}(Q)$ can be Fourier transformed to yield $g_{\alpha\beta}(r)$ through the relation,

$$g_{\alpha\beta}(r) = 1 + \frac{V}{2\pi^2 N r} \int dQ (S_{\alpha\beta}(Q) - 1) Q \sin Qr. \quad (3)$$

The function $g_{\alpha\beta}(r)$ represents the probability that there is an atom of type β at a distance r if there is one of type α at the origin. The peak positions in $g_{\alpha\beta}(r)$ correspond to preferred inter-atomic correlations between α and β atoms. The coordination number (CN), \bar{n}_{α}^{β} for species of type β around a species of type α in the range $r_1 < r < r_2$ is related to the area under the peak, and can be determined from the pair distribution function (PDF), $g_{\alpha\beta}(r)$,

$$\bar{n}_{\alpha}^{\beta} = 4 \pi \rho c_{\beta} \int_{r_1}^{r_2} r^2 g_{\alpha\beta}(r) dr, \quad (4)$$

where ρ is the total number density in \AA^{-3} . For a liquid comprising of m independent species the total number of $g_{\alpha\beta}(r)$'s are $m(m+1)/2$, and this number becomes proportionately greater in more complex ionic liquids. The b_{α} 's are independent of Q , the scattering vector for neutrons, i.e. the scattering is isotropic, and depend on Q for

X-rays, i.e. the scattering is anisotropic. It is this property that facilitates the direct determination of atomic scale structure by neutron diffraction.

Neutrons :

Although ND studies at the total structure function level of a large number of ionic liquids have been carried out, atomic scale models are required to assist in the interpretation of such single diffraction patterns. By contrast, the difference methods of ND (NDIS) are ideally suited to the determination of structure either in terms of individual PDFs, $g_{\alpha\beta}(r)$'s or as linear combinations of the form $\bar{G}_\alpha(r)$, which is specific to the isotopically substituted species, α , and is a weighted combination of the corresponding partial distribution functions, $g_{\alpha\beta}(r)$ (see eq. (7)). Since these PDFs are the first in a hierarchy of inter-atomic correlations, they are the only ones directly accessible from experiments, computer simulations, and theory. The information obtained in an NDIS experiment can thus provide a critical test of model potentials used in computer simulations and liquid state theories⁹.

The last term on the right hand side of eq. (1) defines the total structure factor, $F(Q)$,

$$F(Q) = \sum_{\alpha} \sum_{\beta} c_{\alpha} c_{\beta} b_{\alpha} b_{\beta} (S_{\alpha\beta}(Q) - 1), \quad (5)$$

which is a linear combination of contributions from pairs of different atom types (α , β) weighted by their scattering lengths (b_i 's) and concentrations (atomic fractions), c_i 's. The Fourier transform of $F(Q)$ is $G(r)$, the total radial distribution function (RDF), which can be written as a linear combination (or weighted sum) of all the partial PDFs, $g_{\alpha\beta}(r)$,

$$G(r) = \sum_{\alpha} \sum_{\beta} c_{\alpha} c_{\beta} \bar{b}_{\alpha} \bar{b}_{\beta} (g_{\alpha\beta}(r) - 1). \quad (6)$$

The results from neutron diffraction experiments performed on two samples, identical except for the isotopic composition of one of the species, may be combined to give the first-order difference function,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{\alpha}(Q) &= F(Q) - F'(Q) \\ &= \sum_{\beta} A_{\beta} [S_{\alpha\beta}(Q) - 1], \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

with,

$$A_{\beta} \begin{cases} = 2c_{\alpha} c_{\beta} b_{\beta} (b_{\alpha} - b_{\alpha'}), \beta \neq \alpha \\ = c_{\alpha}^2 [(b_{\alpha})^2 - (b_{\beta})^2], \beta = \alpha, \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where b_{α} and $b_{\alpha'}$ are the mean coherent scattering lengths of the substituted species in the two samples. The Fourier transform of $\Delta_{\alpha}(Q)$ gives $\bar{G}_{\alpha}(r)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{G}_{\alpha}(r) &= \frac{1}{2\pi^2 \rho} \int_0^{\infty} \Delta_{\alpha}(Q) Q^2 dQ \frac{\sin(Qr)}{Qr} \\ &= \sum_{\beta} A_{\beta} [g_{\alpha\beta}(r) - 1]. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

An important property of the difference function, $\Delta_{\alpha}(Q)$, is that the inelasticity corrections¹⁰ to a first-order approximation, being identical for both the samples, should cancel to give a negligible contribution from the inelastic term in eq. (5). The validity of this approximation can be checked as follows. Since $g_{\alpha\beta}(r) = 0$ at r -values below the distance of closest approach of the α and β species (i.e. r_{\min}), $\bar{G}_{\alpha}(r)$ should be equal to the calculated limit,

$$\bar{G}_{\alpha}(0) = - \sum_{\beta} A_{\beta} \quad (10)$$

at low r . In practice, $\bar{G}_{\alpha}(r)$ will oscillate about this value owing to statistical noise on the Q -space data, truncation of the data at finite Q -value, and systematic errors. However, if these effects are small, setting $\bar{G}_{\alpha}(r)$ equal to the $\bar{G}_{\alpha}(0)$ limit for $r \leq r_{\min}$ and back Fourier transformation will yield the Q -space functions in close agreement with the original first-order difference functions from which they are derived. It should be noted that the recoil (inelastic) effect is small for a heavy nucleus, but for lighter nuclei such as H and D, the recoil is large. If a peak in $\bar{G}_{\alpha}(r)$ can be identified with some specific interaction and is completely separable then suitable integration limits can be chosen to obtain the coordination number (CN) of β species around α ,

$$\text{eff } \bar{n}_{\alpha}^{\beta} = \frac{4\pi \rho c_{\beta}}{A_{\beta}} \int_{r_1}^{r_2} [\bar{G}_{\alpha}(r) - \bar{G}_{\alpha}(0)] r^2 dr. \quad (11)$$

The superscript 'eff' in eq. (11) indicates the possibility of multiple contributions to the peak. It may be stressed that this method of evaluating the CN gives the correct value if and only if the following conditions are satisfied:

- left- and right-hand wings of the peak should return to their $\bar{G}_{\alpha}(0)$ values,
- there are no spurious shoulders on either side of the concerned peak,
- the peak is not affected by the spurious oscillations caused by the Fourier transformation of the

truncated Q -space data,

- low- and high- r limits, r_1 and r_2 , of integration should be exactly known, and
- especially, if no other atomic-pair contributes to the same peak.

Second- or higher-order differences between two $\Delta_\alpha(Q)$ in a manner similar to the first-order differences can, in theory, be performed to extract the individual $g_{\alpha\beta}(r)$. However, extreme care is required while working with higher order differences because the contribution of an individual partial to the difference function becomes, in least favourable cases, comparable to the errors associated with it. Thus, small errors in calculating the corrections to the observed intensity, data normalisation, or presence of some systematic errors may prevent accurate determination of an individual $g_{\alpha\beta}(r)$.

The NDIS method is most conveniently illustrated by reference to a simple binary ionic liquid MX_n for which there are three partial structure factors (PSFs), $S_{\text{MX}}(Q)$, $S_{\text{XX}}(Q)$, and $S_{\text{MM}}(Q)$. The matrix elements describing the weighting of the three PSFs to the total $F(Q)$ (see eq. (5)) can be written as,

$$F(Q) = c_M^2 b_M^2 [S_{\text{MM}}(Q) - 1] + c_X^2 b_X^2 [S_{\text{XX}}(Q) - 1] + 2c_M c_X b_M b_X (S_{\text{MX}}(Q) - 1). \quad (12)$$

If scattering lengths of one or both the components can be varied in such a way so as to obtain three experimental total structure factors, $F_1(Q)$, $F_2(Q)$ and $F_3(Q)$, which are sufficiently different to enable three linear equations to be simultaneously solved for $S_{\text{MM}}(Q)$, $S_{\text{XX}}(Q)$ and $S_{\text{MX}}(Q)$, all the PSFs may be extracted. In matrix notation, we may write,

$$|C| |X(Q)| = |F(Q)|, \quad (13)$$

where, if isotopic substitutions were made only on the element M ,

$$|C| = \begin{vmatrix} c_M^2 b_{M,1}^2 & c_X^2 b_X^2 & 2c_M c_X b_{M,1} b_X \\ c_M^2 b_{M,2}^2 & c_X^2 b_X^2 & 2c_M c_X b_{M,2} b_X \\ c_M^2 b_{M,3}^2 & c_X^2 b_X^2 & 2c_M c_X b_{M,3} b_X \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} & c_{13} \\ c_{21} & c_{22} & c_{23} \\ c_{31} & c_{32} & c_{33} \end{vmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

$$|X(Q)| = \begin{vmatrix} S_{\text{MM}}(Q) - 1 \\ S_{\text{XX}}(Q) - 1 \\ S_{\text{MX}}(Q) - 1 \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} X_1(Q) \\ X_2(Q) \\ X_3(Q) \end{vmatrix}, \quad \text{and} \quad (15)$$

$$|F(Q)| = \begin{vmatrix} F_1(Q) \\ F_2(Q) \\ F_3(Q) \end{vmatrix}. \quad (16)$$

The inverse matrix for the solution of these equations is,

$$|X(Q)| = |C|^{-1} |F(Q)|, \quad (17)$$

which can be worked out to extract the individual PSFs, $S_{\alpha\beta}(Q)$, and by Fourier transformation the corresponding PDFs, $g_{\text{MX}}(r)$, $g_{\text{XX}}(r)$ and $g_{\text{MM}}(r)$. As we show by giving examples in the Results and discussion subsections, the isotopic substitution procedure and the difference techniques of ND have been employed successfully to determine the structure of a large number of ionic liquids by simplifying the complexity of overlapping correlations associated with a single ND measurement at the total structure factor, $F(Q)$ level. The experimental acquisition of the individual PDFs between all the pairs of elements in an ionic liquid however still remains largely a challenge, and the complexity of the situation increases with increase in the number of distinct atomic species present. Selective H/D isotopic substitution, for example, on complex cations or anions in room temperature ionic liquids, such as those on imidazolium ion¹¹ in a model ionic liquid dimethylimidazolium chloride, can help to impose additional experimental constraints on the models employed at the atomic level for a detailed structural elucidation of these liquids.

The success of NDIS experiments, however, depends crucially on several other factors. These include, (i) high quality and well characterised samples whose composition is accurately known in terms of atomic concentration and isotope content, (ii) a high flux neutron source that can provide sufficient statistical accuracy in the data, and (iii) stable instrumentation so that data are highly reproducible during the course of an experiment, which takes typically ~10–12 h per sample. Results of NDIS experiments can also be usefully compared with information on liquid structure obtained from other methods.

When the individual PDFs, $g_{\alpha\beta}(r)$ cannot be satisfactorily extracted by the isotopic substitution (NDIS) experiments, the structural parameters such as inter-atomic distances and CNs are derived from the total structure factor, $F(Q)$. It is usual then to fit this function with

various models of the ionic-liquid structure. However, one has to be careful here because without the benefits of isotopic substitution, the total structure factor comprising of several partial structure factors may produce significant cancellation effects with much of the structure remaining hidden. The total diffraction patterns from ionic liquids with strong charge ordering can thus be easily misinterpreted due to charge-induced mutual cancellation of important structural features. When the structural parameters are derived from the total RDFs, $G(r)$, or $\bar{G}_\alpha(r)$ (eq. (9)) where several atom-pairs may contribute to a given peak, the functions $G(r)-G(0)$ or $\bar{G}_\alpha(r)-\bar{G}_\alpha(0)$ are usually fitted^{12,13} by a sum of Gaussians of the form,

$$f_i(r) = \frac{A}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp \left[-\frac{(r - r_{\max})^2}{2\sigma^2} \right]. \quad (18)$$

The fitted parameters A , σ , and r_{\max} of each Gaussian then yield the area, half-width at half-maximum (HWHM) and mean position, respectively, of each peak.

The method of neutron diffraction and isomorphic substitution can also be used to reveal the nanoscopic structure in ionic liquids, but the technique is based on the assumption that isomorphism exists between the pairs of substituted ions, which should possess the same effective size and charge in the ionic liquid. The technique can be used provided there is a large enough difference in the coherent scattering lengths between the atomic nuclei of the substituted species. For example, the two cations, La^{3+} and Ce^{3+} , have significantly different scattering lengths (La : 8.24 barns, Ce : 4.84 barns), similar chemical and physical properties, comparable ionic radii (6-coordinate : 1.17 and 1.15 Å, and 8-coordinate : 1.30 and 1.28 Å, respectively), and their trifluorides crystallise in the same structure where the geometry of the metal (La/Ce) is 9-coordinate tricapped trigonal prismatic. Their isomorphic nature is already established¹⁴ in trichloride, tribromide and triiodide high-temperature ionic liquids (see Results and discussion subsection). If isomorphism in their trifluoride ionic melts can be established, difference techniques of ND can be employed usefully to simplify the complexity of overlapping correlations associated with a single ND measurement at the total $F(Q)$ level. Once isomorphism is established, diffraction data are gathered on the two ionic liquids under similar conditions. A first-order difference is then taken which includes pair-wise structural information specific to the isomorphic species. The advantages of this method are that relatively inexpensive samples are required and deeper insight on ionic liquid structure can be gained than is

possible from a single total ND experiment.

X-Rays :

X-Ray diffraction techniques have been in use since the 1930s to study the liquid structure¹⁵. In general a total X-ray diffraction pattern from an ionic liquid sample is a linear combination of PSFs weighted by the corresponding form factors (eq. (1)). Because of the Q -dependence of the form factors, direct determination of PDFs is not possible and models based on solid-state information are often employed in the data analysis. In order to obtain more definitive structural information from X-ray scattering, three different experimental techniques have been devised.

The first of these is the X-ray diffraction and isomorphic substitution, which should be carried out, whenever possible, in combination with the NDIS on one of the species to ensure that isomorphism exists between the two substituted species. Although this technique has been satisfactorily employed^{16,17} in aqueous electrolyte solutions of Ni^{2+} and Mg^{2+} , it does not seem to have been used so far on ionic liquids of the type under discussion in this article.

The other two X-ray methods exploit the fact that the scattering of X-rays by atoms is strongly modified when the X-ray energy, E (or wavelength, λ), is close to an atomic absorption edge. In this case, the total atomic form factor f , characterizing the interaction between X-rays and the electrons of the atom, is given by,

$$f(Q, E) = f_0(Q) + f'(Q, E) + if''(Q, E), \quad (19)$$

where $f_0(Q)$ is the normal atomic form factor, and $f'(Q, E)$ and $f''(Q, E)$ are the dispersion corrections, that account for resonant scattering processes. The energy dependent terms are called 'anomalous', and these can be obtained classically by first measuring the attenuation coefficient, which is directly related to the imaginary component $f''(Q, E)$, and then using a Kramers-Kronig relation to calculate¹⁸ $f'(Q, E)$. The two possibilities of AXD, as termed in this article, or differential anomalous scattering (DAS), which is a true diffraction method, and EXAFS spectroscopy are considered below.

AXD or DAS :

If the energy of the incident X-rays is allowed to change only below the edge it is mainly $f'(Q, E)$ that changes. By fixing E to a value about 5 eV below the absorption edge and varying Q (or θ) as in a normal diffraction experiment, one obtains a first scattering pattern for a given $f'(Q, E)$ for the atom or ion of interest. The value

of E is then altered by a further few hundred eV below the absorption edge to systematically change the $f'(Q, E)$ to a larger value, and a second scattering experiment on the same sample gives a slightly different pattern. The difference between the two scattering patterns is then calculated, and its Fourier transformation related to the structure around the specific atom or ion. The technique is based on principles similar to NDIS, but is not limited by the availability of isotopes. However, it is constrained by the Q -dependent form factors, and is applicable only to atoms or ions with atomic numbers, $Z > 28$, which in turn sets a limit on the Q -range of the diffraction data. The actual structure function, $\bar{G}_\alpha(r)$, calculated from the Fourier transformation of the sum over PSFs, $S_{\alpha\beta}(Q)$, is in fact convoluted with the Q -dependent X-ray atomic form factors. This convolution, in turn, broadens the peaks associated with the real structure as defined by $g_{\alpha\beta}(r)$, and thereby obscures the structural information in the true $G_\alpha(r)$. The peak positions, however, remain unchanged by the convolution process. Despite these drawbacks, it is possible to obtain accurate structural information on interatomic correlations and coordination numbers (CNs). The AXD technique, similar to NDIS, can be used to give structural information around a specific atom type in an ionic liquid.

EXAFS :

The other method is that of EXAFS spectroscopy which exploits energy changes, represented by $f''(Q, E)$ in eq. (19), that occur when X-rays are absorbed in the region of the absorption edge (Table 3) of a particular particle in a system. EXAFS spectroscopy, in contrast to diffraction methods, is strongly model-dependent. Although Fourier transformation procedures are used, the range of ' Q ' (or k) space information is much more limited than in straightforward diffraction. Indeed, the absorption measurement itself has been shown in some cases to change the sample under study due to radiation damage. Nevertheless, for the study of ionic liquids EXAFS is potentially a magnificent tool because it can provide ion-specific short-range structural information, not limited to the pair correlation functions. Although several general problems exist that make data interpretation difficult, significant improvements have been made recently. A review article¹⁹ by Filipponi describes the current state of EXAFS measurements on liquids in general. The measurement of an EXAFS spectrum for one sample at a given temperature is now relatively quick on most modern synchrotron beam lines. Many studies, however, do not concentrate on the analysis of individual EXAFS spectra but rather on dif-

ferences induced by changes in temperature, pressure, composition, etc.

In a simple EXAFS experiment, the sample's absorption coefficient $\mu(E)$ is measured across a constituent atom's absorption edge. The EXAFS oscillation occurs due to the interference resulting from the backscattering of a photoelectron with the excited atom and its local neighbouring atoms. The EXAFS part of the oscillation is believed to start where the single scattering of the photoelectron dominates the multiple scattering processes²⁰. The EXAFS signal, $\chi(k)$, is unique to each material and depends on the electronic and structural properties of the material. The EXAFS signal is defined as

$$\chi(k) = (\mu(E) - \mu_0(E)) / \Delta\mu_{\text{Edge}}, \quad (20)$$

where the photo-wavevector

$$k = \sqrt{2m_e(E - E_0)} / \hbar \quad (21)$$

$\mu_0(E)$ refers to the atomic background, and $\Delta\mu_{\text{Edge}}$, the change in atomic background occurring at the edge. In addition to the difficulties in obtaining an accurate $\chi(k)$, extraction of the structural properties is often difficult, complicated, and non-unique. The problem is accentuated by the smoothness of the atomic absorption background, strongly perturbed by double electron effects called 'shake-up' and 'shake-off' processes. Apart from a few elements having simple gaseous forms this background contamination is hard to evaluate. Theoretical and experimental approaches are only now beginning to make progress.

Theoretically, the approximation developed²¹ by Sayers *et al.* for the sum averaged over all photo-absorbing atoms gives for the K-edge,

$$\chi(k) = \sum_j S_0^2 \frac{1}{kR_j^2} e^{-2R_j/\lambda_j(k)} |f_j(k)| \sin(2kR_j + 2\delta_1(k) + \varphi_j(k)) \cdot e^{-2\sigma_j^2 k^2},$$

+ multiple scatter terms (22)

where R_j is the distance to the j -th atom, δ_1 is the phase shift for the $I = 1$ phase shift of the photo absorbing atom, $\lambda_j(k)$ is the mean-free path of the photoelectron, $|f_j(k)|$ and $\varphi_j(k)$ are, respectively, the back scattering amplitude and phase function of the atom j . The EXAFS Debye-Waller term, $e^{-2\sigma_j^2 k^2}$, is used to take into account the vibration of the atom at position j because it models a

Gaussian vibration about its center of mass. Since this is not realistic for most atoms, the term has been generalized into the cumulant expansion, with the introduction of more fitting parameters²². This also illustrates why the EXAFS signal from liquids is generally much weaker than that from a solid, because the disorder washes out the signal.

For a multicomponent ionic liquid, eq. (22) rewritten^{23,24} in terms of $\chi_\alpha(k)$ characterizes the EXAFS signal from atom α ,

$$\chi_\alpha(k) = \sum_{\beta} \int_0^{\infty} dr \left(4\pi r^2 \rho_{\beta} \gamma_{\alpha\beta}(k, r) g_{\alpha\beta}(r) + O(g^3(r)) \right) \quad (23)$$

+ higher order terms

where the sum is taken over all independent atomic species, and ρ_{β} is the number density of β atoms. The integral replaces the sum in eq. (22) and the integrand accounts for the diffuse liquid structure in terms of a product of the partial pair RDFs, $g_{\alpha\beta}(r)$, and the term $\gamma_{\alpha\beta}$ which is calculated theoretically and represents the effective EXAFS scattering from atoms α and β . $g^3(r)$ represents the triplet distribution functions of the system.

Even after the higher order terms are dropped, the calculation of the $g(r)$ remains ill determined for a number of reasons²⁵. The first problem to consider is the fact that E_0 is unknown because the edge shifts as a function of the chemical bonding, and the EXAFS function involves a coupled structural and dynamic equation. It has been shown that for ions forming complexes, the multiple scattering terms have a significant contribution to the signal. This causes further problems because the extent to which multiple scattering contributes is strongly dependent on the precise bonding angle and the distribution of these angles in the ensemble average. This can, in part, be overcome by obtaining longer k -space data and by improving the signal-to-noise ratio of the measured spectra. However it still remains a problem, not necessarily solvable with standard EXAFS experimental methods alone. Additional problems arise due to the S_0 factor, which accounts for many-body loss effects. It is often freely fitted in an appropriate range, thereby reducing the overall signal and causing problems in the absolute determination of coordination numbers.

The current analysis methods for experimental EXAFS data from disordered materials follow one of several ba-

sic procedures. The approach most akin to the ordered materials is to generate a model of the local environment, and then calculate the expected EXAFS signal. For liquids, however, adding a disorder term, and making small changes to the individual atom positions within the cluster model while at the same time comparing the calculated EXAFS with the experimental data refines this model. There have also been several successful attempts in taking model $g(r)$'s from molecular dynamics (MD) simulations of liquids. These models are then refined²⁶⁻²⁸ to fit the experimental EXAFS data. Preference should be given to data analyzed in this way because the EXAFS measurement, unlike a diffraction measurement, does not have sensitivity to the absolute density because the electro-path is always too short. It has been shown²⁹ that the measured coordination number changes significantly if the tail of the $g(r)$ is considered in the analysis of liquid EXAFS. An analysis procedure to extract pair correlation functions of liquids and disordered binary mixtures from XAFS data, satisfying both long-distance behaviour and long-wavelength limit of Bhatia-Thornton structure factors, has recently been reported³⁰.

2. Results and discussion

Each of the methods discussed above has been used with varying degrees of success to obtain structural information on a variety of ionic liquids as discussed below. The structural results inferred from less direct techniques, such as Raman spectroscopy, are not included here. In some cases the results have been combined with MD simulations in order to deepen our knowledge of structure in specific systems. Besides the results published in the literature and many of the conference proceedings, a rich source of additional information is available in the form of published Annual Reports of the various Neutron and X-ray facilities (see Table 4). These publications con-

Table 3. X-Ray absorption energies in keV of some chosen elements at the K, L_I, L_{II} and L_{III}-edges

Element/(At. No., Z)	K, L _I , L _{II} , L _{III} -edges/(keV)
K (19)	3.607, 0.341, 0.297, 0.295
Cu (29)	8.979, 1.100, 0.952, 0.932
Br (35)	13.474, 1.782, 1.596, 1.550
Rb (37)	15.200, 2.065, 1.863, 1.805
Y (39)	17.080, 2.373, 2.156, 2.080
Ag (47)	25.514, 3.806, 3.524, 3.351
La (57)	38.925, 6.267, 5.891, 5.483
Nd (60)	43.569, 7.126, 6.722, 6.208
Dy (66)	53.789, 9.047, 8.581, 7.790

tain progress reports on the status of experiments and describe the state-of-the-art methods being employed to tackle many topical problems. The acquisition of PSFs and corresponding PDFs of all the pairs of elements of an ionic liquid, however, still remains a formidable challenge.

Table 4. A non-exhaustive list providing links to some of the leading neutron and X-ray sources in Europe, Japan, and the US

Source	Address
Neutrons	http://www.isis.rl.ac.uk/
	http://www.ill.fr/
	http://www-llb.cea.fr/index_e.html/
	http://neutron-www.kek.jp/
	http://www.pns.anl.gov/
X-Rays	http://www.diamond.ac.uk/
	http://www.esrf.fr/
	http://www.spring8.jp/top.html/
	http://www.aps.anl.gov/aps/
	http://www.srs.ac.uk/srs/

Molten monovalent-metal halides (MX) and their mixtures :

Structural properties of all the molten alkali metal chlorides, $\text{LiCl}^{31,32}$, $\text{NaCl}^{33,34}$, KCl^{35} , RbCl^{36} , and $\text{CsCl}^{35,37}$, determined by the NDIS are typical of loosely coordinated structure. The partial structure factors of molten NaCl^{34} , which is typical of a molten alkali metal chloride, are shown in Fig. 1. All of these systems show (see e.g. Fig. 1) a deep "Coulombic dip" in the cation-anion structure factor, $S_{+-}(Q)$, lying in phase with the main "Coulombic" peaks in $S_{--}(Q)$ and $S_{++}(Q)$, a feature representative of simple Coulombic ordering, and the PDFs, $g_{++}(r)$ and $g_{--}(r)$, being phased to give complete charge cancellation for large r -values, a feature characteristic of complete ionisation in these ionic liquids. Theoretical models based on Fumi-Tosi potentials can adequately describe^{38,39} the above structural features of these 1 : 1 ionic melts.

Fig. 2 compares the PDFs, $g_{++}(r)$, $g_{--}(r)$, and $g_{+-}(r)$, respectively, of molten NaCl determined from NDIS studies^{33,34} with those obtained from MD computer simulations³⁸ and liquid-state structural theory³⁹, and the agreement seems to be very good.

By the same NDIS methods, molten $\text{CuCl}^{40,41}$, CuBr^{42} and AgCl^{43} are shown to possess characteristics typical of weakly ionic systems. The PDFs for these systems show a deep penetration of M^+ ions into the first coordi-

Fig. 1. The partial structure factors (PSFs), $S_{\alpha\beta}(Q)$ of molten NaCl at 875°C ; after Biggin and Enderby³⁴.

Fig. 2. The pair distribution functions (PDFs) of molten NaCl from neutron diffraction³⁴ (circles), computer simulations³⁸ (dots) and liquid-state structural theory³⁹ (curves); after Ballone *et al.*³⁹.

nation shell of the M^+ ion, a considerable asymmetry between M-M and Cl-Cl PDFs, and almost featureless $g_{++}(r)$ and $S_{++}(Q)$. The PDFs of molten CuCl are shown in Fig. 3 as an illustration. These features are different from those observed in molten alkali metal halides. Although, theoretical models based on simple ionic pair-potentials can still reproduce the gross structural features of these melts, polarization effects cannot be neglected in the model potentials. The structural results from total ND measurements on molten CuX and AgX ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$), and on mixed molten salts $(\text{CuCl})_x-(\text{CuBr})_{1-x}$ and $(\text{AgBr})_x-(\text{AgI})_{1-x}$ have also been reported⁴⁴.

The three PSFs and corresponding PDFs in molten

Fig. 3. The pair radial distribution functions (PDFs) of molten CuCl at 500°C; after Eisenberg *et al.*⁴¹.

CuBr have been extracted⁴⁵ from AXD, and the structural characteristics are found to be similar to those obtained by using the NDIS technique. The use of 3rd generation synchrotron X-ray sources has been demonstrated⁴⁶ to determine the PSFs of CuBr and RbBr by AXS. The three PSFs in molten CuBr and CuI have been determined⁴⁷ by combining AXD results with RMC modeling. The EXAFS technique has been used to calculate the partial PDFs in molten KBr, RbBr and CuBr⁴⁸⁻⁵¹, RbCl^{52,53}, and these PDFs have then been compared with those obtained from the NDIS and/or MD simulations. AgBr in both the solid and liquid phases has been investigated⁵⁴ using EXAFS with simultaneous analysis of both the Ag and Br K-edges (see Table 3). It is reported that the double-edge refinement leads to a considerable improvement in the results over the previous data using standard data-analysis procedures. CuI has been investigated⁵⁵ over a wide temperature range 298–903 K in the solid, high-temperature superionic, and liquid phases by X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) at Cu and I K-edges. The local structures of molten CsCl and 2 CsCl-NaCl investigated⁵⁶ recently by using the Cs-K X-ray absorption edge reveal the nearest-neighbour Cs⁺-Cl⁻ distances and CNs to be 3.26 Å (5.44) and 3.22 Å (5.85), respectively, thereby suggesting a 6-fold coordination of Cs⁺ in both the systems. The results for CsCl compare well with the NDIS results, 3.4 Å (5.8). The structural results from XRD measurements on a large number of 1 : 1 halide melts such as LiF, LiCl, LiBr, LiI, NaF, NaCl, NaI, KF, KCl, KBr, CsBr, CsI, and AgCl have also been compiled and discussed⁵⁷.

Molten divalent-metal halides (MX₂) and their mixtures :

A number of 2 : 1 halide melts⁵⁸⁻⁶⁵ including MgCl₂, CaCl₂, BaCl₂, SrCl₂, ZnCl₂, and NiX₂ (X = Cl, Br and I) have been studied by the NDIS technique, and others

such as MnCl₂, ZnBr₂ and ZnI₂, investigated by the total ND measurements. The structural features in the PSFs of molten alkaline-earth metal chlorides reveal that the principal peaks in $S_{++}(Q)$ here lie neither in phase with the peaks in $S_{--}(Q)$ nor with the valleys in the cross-term structure factors, $S_{+-}(Q)$. This behaviour is in contrast to that observed in molten alkali-metal chlorides, and suggests that the Coulombic ordering of the two ionic species clearly observed in the case of the alkali-metal halides is disturbed by the relatively strong Coulombic repulsions between the divalent cations. Although a simple ionic pair-potential still reproduces the broad features of structural ordering in these MCl₂ melts, significant discrepancies at a quantitative level^{66,67} between the computed and experimental data now become apparent.

Fig. 4 shows as an illustration the PSFs of molten SrCl₂ determined⁶⁰ from NDIS studies, and the results are compared with those obtained⁶⁶ from computer simulations and liquid-state structural theory⁶⁷. In contrast to the structural features observed in the PSFs of molten NaCl (see Fig. 1), the principal peak in $S_{SrSr}(Q)$ is higher and sharper than that in $S_{ClCl}(Q)$ and neither lies in phase with it nor with the valley in $S_{SrCl}(Q)$. The main valley in the cross-term structure factor, $S_{SrCl}(Q)$ lies at Q -values intermediate between the positions of principal peaks in like-ion structure factors. Similar behaviour is observed for other alkaline-earth metal chlorides, such as BaCl₂⁶¹. Coulombic repulsions between divalent cations in molten BaCl₂ and SrCl₂, for example, lead to a cation-cation distance of ~5 Å, which is larger as compared to ~4 Å in molten NaCl.

The structural behaviour of molten ZnCl₂⁶², quite different from the other 2 : 1 melts such as BaCl₂ and SrCl₂

Fig. 4. The partial structure factors (PSFs) of molten SrCl₂ from neutron diffraction⁶⁰ (circles), computer simulations⁶⁶ (dots) and liquid-state structural theory⁶⁷ (curves); after Pastore *et al.*⁶⁷.

discussed above, shows (see Fig. 5) that the principal peaks in $S_{\text{ClCl}}(Q)$ and $S_{\text{ZnZn}}(Q)$ are again, as in molten alkali-metal halides (see Fig. 1), in phase with each other and also with the valley in the cross-term structure factor, $S_{\text{ZnCl}}(Q)$. In contrast to the SrCl_2 case (see Fig. 4), the principal peak in $S_{\text{ClCl}}(Q)$ in this case is higher and sharper than that in $S_{\text{ZnZn}}(Q)$.

However, an additional feature called "First Sharp Diffraction Peak" (FSDP) or "pre-peak" has now appeared at $Q \approx 1 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ in all the partial structure factors, more prominently so in the metal-metal term, $S_{\text{ZnZn}}(Q)$ (see Fig. 5). An interesting aspect of ND structural data on 2 : 1 and also 3 : 1 (see later) molten metal halides is the appearance of this FSDP, which is linked to the existence of intermediate range order (IRO) in these melts, and it is found to be absent in the diffraction patterns of 1 : 1

Fig. 5. The partial structure factors (PSFs), $S_{\alpha\beta}(Q)$ for molten ZnCl_2 ; after Biggin and Enderby⁶².

halide melts. All the three zinc halide melts⁶⁴, ZnX_2 ($X = \text{Cl, Br and I}$), for example, show a well resolved pre-peak in the total structure factors, $F(Q)$. A significant shift in the position of the pre-peak to a lower Q -value and an increase in its height occur with increase in the anion size or with decreasing ionicity from chloride to bromide to iodide. A similar trend in the position and height of the pre-peak with increase in anion size is also found in molten NiX_2 ($X = \text{Cl, Br, and I}$) systems^{63,65,68,69}.

With the change in the cation size, the ionic melts of stoichiometry MX_2 show (see Fig. 6) an intriguing evolution of short- and intermediate-range order structure,

which has been successfully reproduced⁷⁰ by potentials based on polarisable ion model (PIM). For instance, as the cation size decreases from Ba (1.35 Å) → Sr (1.12 Å) → Ca (0.99 Å) → Zn (0.74 Å), the CN, n_{+-} decreases, respectively, from 7.7 → 6.9 → 5.4 → ~4, and the first peak in $g_{++}(r)$ shifts markedly inwards relative to that in $g_{--}(r)$ to an extent that in CaCl_2 and ZnCl_2 these peaks, contrary to the requirements of maximising the separation between the doubly charged cations, coincide (Fig. 6). Also, with a decrease in the cation size the nearest-neighbour shell in $g_{+-}(r)$ becomes progressively better defined with lesser penetration of like ions into the first coordination shell of unlike pairs. While in the case of BaCl_2 , SrCl_2 , and CaCl_2 , penetration effects play a major role in determining their static structure and dynamic behaviour, the PDFs of molten ZnCl_2 show virtually no such penetration of like ions into the nearest-neighbour shells. Also, the PDFs of molten ZnCl_2 reveal that the four chloride ions provide a tetrahedral site for each zinc ion, that the nearest neighbour distances, $r_{\text{Zn-Zn}} = r_{\text{Cl-Cl}}$, and that there is no exchange of ions between the first shell and the surrounding liquid. These results are a clear testimony to the existence of highly stable tetrahedral, ZnCl_4^{2-} structural units, which tend to form a network

Fig. 6. The pair radial distribution functions, PDFs: $g_{+-}(r)$ (full curve), $g_{--}(r)$ (broken curve) and $g_{++}(r)$ (dotted curve) for molten (a) BaCl_2 ⁶¹, (c) CaCl_2 ⁵⁹ and (d) ZnCl_2 ⁶² from NDIS studies. The PDFs for molten SrCl_2 in (b) from NDIS studies⁶⁰ (circles), liquid-state structural theory⁶⁷ (curves) and computer simulations⁶⁶ (dots): $g_{+-}(r)$ (left curves), $g_{--}(r)$ (right curves) and $g_{++}(r)$ (inset); after Pastore *et al.*⁶⁷.

via chlorine sharing linkages. Such a network results in a state of pronounced IRO giving rise to the appearance of the FSDP in the structure factor data as mentioned earlier. Computer simulations based on a simple Rigid Ion Model (RIM) have failed to reproduce the evolution of short- and intermediate-range order discussed above.

A new analysis of the old ND data on molten ZnCl_2 by using a recently developed method based on Empirical Potential Structure Refinement (EPSR) reports⁷¹ that there are significant uncertainties in the extracted partials, especially the Zn-Zn term due to the small weighting of this PSF to the total structure function and due to systematic uncertainties in the original experimental data. Molten ZnCl_2 , RbCl and Rb_2ZnCl_4 have been investigated^{52,53} by the EXAFS technique. The results show the existence of isolated ZnCl_4 tetrahedral units, and an absence of the tetrahedral network in Rb_2ZnCl_4 , which dominates the structure in pure ZnCl_2 melt. Molten Rb_2ZnCl_4 can, thus, be considered to be a mixture of the two binary melts in which RbCl acts as a network breaker. These results are consistent with those obtained from ND studies on ZnCl_2 - LiCl and ZnCl_2 - KCl mixed melts^{65,72,73}. ND structural studies on NiCl_2 - LiCl and NiCl_2 - KCl have also been reported^{65,73}. XAFS study⁷⁴ at the Zn and Br K-edges of molten ZnBr_2 reveals the presence of ZnBr_4^{2-} tetrahedral units sharing a Br^- ion. Analyses of the local structures of ZnBr_2 - KBr melts by XRD, Raman spectroscopy, and molecular orbital calculations show⁷⁵ that the 3-D network clusters formed by sharing a common Br atom between the individual ZnBr_4^{2-} tetrahedral units are broken into discrete units on the addition of KBr . Similar conclusions are reached from the ND studies⁷⁶ of ZnBr_2 - KBr melts. Short-range structures⁷⁷ of ZnBr_2 - ZnCl_2 melts by ND in conjunction with other techniques as in Ref.⁷⁵ show the presence of ligand-substituted tetrahedral structural units, $[\text{ZnCl}_n\text{Br}_{4-n}]^{2-}$ ($n = 0-4$) rather than simple mixing of $[\text{ZnCl}_4]^{2-}$ and $[\text{ZnBr}_4]^{2-}$ units. A new high temperature-high pressure apparatus⁷⁸ for ND experiments on corrosive samples up to 900 K and pressures up to 3 K bar has been tested, and used to determine the structure factors at five different thermodynamic states of molten ZnCl_2 at 723 K up to pressures of 4 K bar.

The structural results from XRD on a large number of molten 2 : 1 metal halides and their mixtures with alkali-metal halides such as CaCl_2 , $(\text{LiCl})_x(\text{CaCl}_2)_{(1-x)}$ ($x = 0.67, 0.50$), $(\text{NaCl})_x(\text{CaCl}_2)_{(1-x)}$ ($x = 0.67, 0.50, 0.33$), $(\text{KCl})_{0.67}(\text{BaCl}_2)_{0.33}$, MnCl_2 , $(\text{LiCl})_{0.67}(\text{MnCl}_2)_{0.33}$, $(\text{KCl})_{0.67}(\text{MnCl}_2)_{0.33}$, ZnCl_2 , $(\text{KCl})_x(\text{ZnCl}_2)_{(1-x)}$ ($x = 0.67, 0.50, 0.33$), CoCl_2 , PbCl_2 , $(\text{LiCl})_x(\text{PbCl}_2)_{(1-x)}$

($x = 0.50, 0.33$), ZnBr_2 , BeF_2 , $(\text{LiF})_x(\text{BeF}_2)_{(1-x)}$ ($x = 0.80, 0.67, 0.50$), $(\text{NaF})_x(\text{BeF}_2)_{(1-x)}$ ($x = 0.67, 0.50, 0.33$), and $(\text{KF})_{0.5}(\text{BeF}_2)_{0.5}$ have been compiled⁵⁷.

ND studies on molten PbCl_2 and PbBr_2 show⁷⁹ that although their crystal structures are similar, the short-range structure in the two melts is quite different. In particular, the CN of Cl around Pb are reported to be 4 at $2.84 \text{ \AA} + \sim 2$ at 3.40 \AA , both peaks in the total $G(r)$ are thought to form the 1st coordination shell. In contrast, the Br CN around Pb is estimated to be ~ 4 . XRD and XAFS analyses of molten PbCl_2 show⁸⁰, similar to the above observations by ND, that the first coordination shell of Pb^{2+} consists of 4 Cl^- rigidly bound and 2-3 other Cl^- bound loosely at a larger distance. XAFS studies on PbF_2 and $x \text{ PbF}_2 + (1-x) \text{ LiF}$ ($x = 0.6$) at the L_{III} -edge of Pb reveal⁸¹ that the nearest-neighbour Pb^{2+} - F^- distance and the corresponding CN are 2.36 \AA and 6, respectively for molten $\text{PbF}_2 + \text{LiF}$, and 2.27 \AA and 4 for molten PbF_2 . These measurements were carried out over a range of temperatures starting from room temperature to above the melting points of the compounds. Distinct phase shifts observed in the XAFS functions suggest superionic conductance transitions in both PbF_2 and $\text{PbF}_2 + \text{LiF}$ between ~ 676 and 777 K . Local structures of CdCl_2 ⁸² by XAFS + XRD and CdBr_2 ⁸³ by XAFS reveal that the nearest-neighbour Cd^{2+} - X^- distances and CNs decrease from 2.61 \AA (6) in the solid to 2.47 - 2.50 \AA (4) in the melt for CdCl_2 , and from 2.71 \AA (6) in the solid phase at RT to 2.60 \AA (4) in the molten state for CdBr_2 . The Sr^{2+} - Cl^- distance and CN in molten SrCl_2 determined⁸⁴ by XAFS are 2.99 \AA and 6.6, respectively.

XAFS measurements on molten EuCl_2 at the Eu-L_{III} edge have been attempted⁸⁵ recently at a number of temperatures in the range 300-1175 K. Extreme care was taken in synthesizing the chemical and preparing the sample pellets with boron nitride (BN) matrix powder in dried Ar atmosphere to avoid moisture and oxygen. Even during XAFS measurements a continuous flow of dried Ar gas was maintained in the hermetically sealed furnace. A distinct phase shift in EXAFS oscillations observed between 700 and 950 K is assigned to the oxidation of Eu^{2+} to Eu^{3+} . From a comparison of the XAFS spectra on EuCl_2 with those on Eu_2O_3 , La_2O_3 , and LaOCl , it is suggested that Eu_2O_3 rather than EuOCl is produced between 700 and 950 K on heating EuCl_2 . It is probable that trace quantities of $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{O}_2$ left in the furnace or absorbed by the sample pellets during their transfer to the furnace may have caused the oxidation of EuCl_2 at high temperature. The presence of Eu_2O_3 , being solid at

these temperatures, precludes the structure determination of pure molten EuCl_2 .

Clearly, there is a need to develop methods to overcome the above difficulties. A measurement system⁸⁶ in which the solid sample sealed in the upper tank of a quartz cell runs down a narrow path (0.1–0.2 mm thickness in the beam) on melting to fill the path and the lower tank, has been suggested and used successfully for hygroscopic samples. However, due to the absorption of the quartz cell, the measurable energy is limited to > 10 keV, and the quartz cell is not obviously suitable to study molten fluorides. A new cell for high temperature EXAFS measurements in molten fluorides has been developed⁸⁷ and tested. In this cell, two plates of pyrolytic boron nitride are fixed hermetically together around the sample in order to avoid any evaporation and atmospheric interaction. It should be noted, however, that the use of hermetically sealed furnace with continuous flushing of dried Ar gas did not prevent oxidation of EuCl_2 , as discussed above.

Molten trivalent-metal halides (MX_3) and their mixtures :

The MX_3 salts are known to undergo a variety of structural transitions (see Table 5) on melting. For instance, we now know that (i) the macroscopic parameters of the melting transition such as melting temperature, T_m , entropy change, ΔS_m and fractional volume change, $\Delta V/V_1$, (ii) the structure of the high-temperature crystal phase before melting and, (iii) the values of transport properties, such as ionic conductivity, σ , and shear viscosity, η , of the melt near freezing, are a good indication of structural ordering in these molten salts.

However, in comparison to a large number of NDIS studies performed on 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 ionic metal-halide melts (see previous sections), the structural data at the PDF level for 3 : 1 molten metal halides is lacking. In fact, molten DyCl_3 is the only 3 : 1 system in which NDIS technique has been successfully employed^{6,88–91} to determine all the three PSFs, $S_{\text{Dy-Dy}}(Q)$, $S_{\text{Dy-Cl}}(Q)$, and $S_{\text{Cl-Cl}}(Q)$, and the corresponding PDFs. As already discussed (see Table 1), there is an intrinsic limitation in the use of the NDIS technique. This is so, because it is possible to prepare suitable samples with high isotopic contrasts in only a few select cases. Apart from molten DyCl_3 , a large number of other molten metal halides of type MX_3 , spanning a wide range of ionic radii, such as chlorides (LaCl_3 ^{92,93}, CeCl_3 ⁹², TbCl_3 ⁹⁴, YCl_3 ^{93–96}, ScCl_3 ^{93,97}, HoCl_3 and ErCl_3 ^{94,98}, AlCl_3 ⁹⁹, SbCl_3 ^{100,101}, FeCl_3 ^{102,103}, BiCl_3 ^{104,105}, InCl_3 ¹⁰⁵, NdCl_3 ¹⁰⁶, and

UCl_3 ^{107,108}), bromides (BiBr_3 ¹⁰⁴, AlBr_3 and GaBr_3 ¹⁰⁹, LaBr_3 and CeBr_3 ⁹², DyBr_3 , YBr_3 , HoBr_3 and ErBr_3 ^{98,110}), and iodides (BiI_3 ¹⁰⁴, GaI_3 ¹⁰⁹, LaI_3 and CeI_3 ⁹², ScI_3 ⁹⁷), have been analyzed at the total ND structure factor, $F(Q)$, or radial distribution function (RDF), $G(r)$, level.

XRD results of MX_3 melts (AlCl_3 ¹¹¹, SbCl_3 ^{100,101}, NdCl_3 ^{57,112,113}, LaCl_3 ^{57,114,115}, LaBr_3 ¹¹⁶, CeCl_3 , PrCl_3 , GdCl_3 , DyCl_3 and SmCl_3 ^{57,112,114}, ErCl_3 ¹¹⁷, UCl_3 ¹¹⁵) have usually been analyzed by a model fitting of the experimental $F(Q)$ using the Debye equation to obtain structural information in terms of the nearest-neighbour distances and CNs. Such studies have been made primarily on laboratory-based equipment. It may be noted that the CNs of metal-Cl pairs obtained in all the above lanthanide and actinide halides from XRD are reported to be six, and the existence of octahedral complex anions, MX_6^{3-} in these MX_3 melts are found to be consistent with the results of Raman spectroscopy. However, the CNs of metal-Cl pairs in LaCl_3 , LaBr_3 and UCl_3 obtained from the above XRD studies are in disagreement with those obtained from recent ND + MD studies.

The experimental results for DyCl_3 and other MX_3 melts have also been complemented with the results obtained from MD simulations for which two separate approaches have been used. Firstly, the Rigid Ion Model (RIM) in which the simulations have been performed by using only the Born-Mayer-like pair potentials,

$$U_{ij}(r_{ij}) = Q_i Q_j / r_{ij} + B_{ij} \exp(-a_{ij} r_{ij}) - C_{ij}^6 / r_{ij}^6 - C_{ij}^8 / r_{ij}^8, \quad (24)$$

which describe the short-range repulsion, dispersion and charge-charge interactions. Formal charges (Q_i) of +3 for the cation and –1 for the anion were used for several of the 3 : 1 halide melts reported here. The short-range repulsion is controlled by two parameters, B_{ij} and a_{ij} related to the ionic radii, σ_i , and a hardness parameter, ρ_i , describing the steepness of the repulsive part of the potential of ion, i . The terms C_{ij}^6 and C_{ij}^8 describe the dispersion effects. The details are described elsewhere^{118,119}. Secondly, those computer simulations where this potential was supplemented by taking into account the polarization effects via the Polarizable Ion Model^{70,120} (PIM). The results of molten DyCl_3 are particularly interesting because these have ramifications in the interpretation of other MX_3 systems discussed later. We shall, therefore, discuss these results here briefly before reviewing the other 3 : 1 molten metal halide systems.

The experimental total structure factors, $F(Q)$, for the three isotopic samples of DyCl_3 show⁸⁹ that the main or

Table 5. Physical properties of some 3 : 1 (MX₃) metal halides

Salt	Crystal structure	Cation radius/Å	T_m /(K)	ΔS_m /(Cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta V/V_1$ (%)	σ /(Ω^{-1} cm ⁻¹)
Chlorides :						
UCl ₃	UCl ₃	1.025	1110	10	11	1.1
LaCl ₃	UCl ₃	1.032	1131	11.5	16.3	1.2-1.5
CeCl ₃	UCl ₃	1.01	1095	11.7	17.9	0.8-1.1
NdCl ₃	UCl ₃	0.983	1032	11.6	22	0.60-0.79
DyCl ₃	AlCl ₃ ^a	0.912	928	6.6	0.34	0.32-0.44
YCl ₃	AlCl ₃	0.90	994	7.6	0.45	0.39
TbCl ₃	^b	0.92	855	5.4	0.2	-
HoCl ₃	AlCl ₃	0.90	993	7.3	1-3	0.39
ErCl ₃	AlCl ₃	0.89	1048	7.4	4.7	0.3-0.4
InCl ₃	AlCl ₃	0.80	859	-	39	0.42
BiCl ₃	BiCl ₃	1.03	507	11.2	22	0.38
ScCl ₃	YCl ₃ ^c	0.75	1212	13.0	32	0.48
AlCl ₃	AlCl ₃	0.54	466	18.1	47	5.0×10^{-7}
FeCl ₃	FeCl ₃	0.55-0.65	577	17.8	39	0.04
SbCl ₃	SbCl ₃	0.76	347	8.7	17	2.0×10^{-4}
Bromides :						
LaBr ₃	UCl ₃	1.032	1061	12.3	12	0.6-0.8
CeBr ₃	UCl ₃	1.01	1005	12.4	12	-
DyBr ₃	FeCl ₃	0.91	1152	-	-	-
YBr ₃	FeCl ₃	0.90	1186	-	-	-
HoBr ₃	FeCl ₃	0.90	1192	-	-	-
ErBr ₃	FeCl ₃	0.89	1196	-	-	-
AlBr ₃	^d	0.54	644	7.3	18	1.0×10^{-8}
Iodides :						
LaI ₃	PuBr ₃	1.032	1051	12.7	24	0.4
CeI ₃	PuBr ₃	1.01	1033	12.0	21	0.4
ScI ₃	FeCl ₃	0.75	1218	15.5	35	-

^aHigh-temperature crystal structure; low-temperature crystal structure : PuBr₃-type.

^bRoom temperature crystal structure : PuBr₃-type; undergoes a solid-solid phase transition at 783 K into an octahedral structure consisting of TbCl₆³⁻.

^cPossible high-temperature crystal type; low-temperature crystal structure : FeCl₃-type.

^dSee text.

predominant contribution to the FSDP at $Q \approx 1 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ is the metal-metal term, and these Dy-Dy correlations exist on the scale of IRO through chlorine-sharing linkages. While the RIM and PIM simulated PDFs, $g_{\text{Dy-Cl}}(r)$ and $g_{\text{Cl-Cl}}(r)$ reproduce⁹⁰ equally well the experimental PDFs, and have similar shapes from the two models, the results for Dy-Dy partial PDF obtained from the two models are quite different (see Fig. 7). The NDIS results show that the first peak in $g_{\text{Dy-Dy}}(r)$ is split into two component distances and the PIM results seem to nicely reproduce the

experimental function^{6,88-91}, thus, highlighting the importance of including polarization effects in the model potential used for computer simulations.

The results reveal that (i) the distribution of anions is hardly affected by the polarization effects and, (ii) although repulsion between triply charged Dy³⁺ ions should maximize the separation between the cations (similar to that observed in the RIM results), this effect is offset by the polarization of anions by triply charged cations, leading to shortened cation-cation distances by the Dy-Cl-Dy

Fig. 7. The partial PDFs for pure molten DyCl_3 : experimental NDIS data (open circles), RIM MD simulation results (solid line), and PIM MD results (dashed line) for (a) Cl-Cl, (b) Dy-Cl, and (c) Dy-Dy correlations. Figure adopted from Ref.⁹⁰.

'bond bending' (see Fig. 8). The first peak in $g_{\text{Dy-Cl}}(r)$ yields a CN of 6, which shows that octahedral coordination in molten DyCl_3 is preserved on melting. Another trend worth noticing (see Fig. 7) is that the main peak in $g_{\text{Dy-Dy}}(r)$ is a doublet. The low- r feature is associated

with a pair of cations connected to each other via a pair of chloride ions while the large- r feature arises from a pair of cations sharing a single anion. It is clear that the shift of the first feature to substantially smaller separations is caused due to the two cations being drawn together by the edge-sharing arrangement between the connected polyhedra.

Fig. 8. An illustration of polarisable ion model (PIM) for octahedral co-ordination of metal ions, Dy^{3+} (small circles) with Cl^- (large circles). The dipole induced by the cation on the anion effectively interposes a negative charge along the line of centres between two cations and, Dy-Cl-Dy bond bending may lead to corner-sharing (I), edge-sharing (II) and face-sharing (III) octahedra. Figure adopted from Ref.⁶.

The dilution of a strongly structured or a network forming lanthanide or actinide chloride melt by an alkali metal chloride should provide a way to probe the stability of the building block (polyhedral unit) in the liquid structure. The role of the alkali halide component is primarily to donate halogens to the polyvalent metal ions while the alkali metal ions act as counter ions providing screening. The formation, co-existence and stability of different complex anions depend strongly on the melt composition and also on the role of the halogen partner and nature of the alkali counter ion. In many systems, there is strong evidence to suggest the presence of complex anions with life times longer than the translational and rotational diffusion times. In network-forming ionic liquids it is commonly observed that addition of a salt with a common anion in combination with a weakly co-ordinating cation breaks down the network structure.

ND studies on $(\text{DyCl}_3)_{0.25}(\text{NaCl})_{0.75}$ mixed melt⁸⁹ at the composition around which the enthalpy of mixing goes through a minimum, indicating compound formation of stoichiometry DyNa_3Cl_6 , have been carried out in

conjunction with the RIM and PIM MD simulations⁹⁰. The results show that the addition of NaCl breaks the octahedral network in pure DyCl₃, and that at ~75% NaCl the concentration of Cl⁻ ions is sufficient to isolate discrete DyCl₆³⁻ octahedral molecular ion units. Interestingly, polarization effects were found to be responsible in promoting such break-up of the network. The first coordination shell, sharply defined by the $g_{\text{Dy-Cl}}(r)$, integrates to give six nearest-neighbours. However, in contrast to the case for the pure DyCl₃ melt (see Fig. 7), the first minimum in $g_{\text{Dy-Cl}}(r)$ in the mixed melt (see Fig. 9) now goes to zero, indicating a very stable coordination complex from which Cl⁻ ions exchange very slowly with the bulk.

Fig. 9. The partial PDF $g_{\text{Dy-Cl}}(r)$, showing how the addition of NaCl to DyCl₃ to form a molten mixture of stoichiometry DyNa₃Cl₆ affects the Dy-Cl correlation. The $g_{\text{Dy-Dy}}(r)$, not shown, in the mixed melt shifts to a much larger separation distance as compared to that in pure molten DyCl₃, indicating the break-up of the network. Figure adopted from Ref.⁹⁰.

The ND measurements on molten LaCl₃ reveal⁹² that the CN of Cl⁻ ions around the cation reduces from 9 in its high-temperature crystalline form to ≈6.4 in its liquid phase. Although the major contribution to the first peak at 2.88 Å in the total RDF is from the La-Cl nearest-neighbours, the peak shows a significant overlap from other pair correlations. However, since these values compare reasonably with those reported earlier ($r_{\text{La-Cl}} = 2.83$ Å, $\bar{n}_{\text{La}}^{\text{Cl}} = 5.7$) from XRD studies⁵⁷, the authors conclude that there is a breakdown in the local structure of LaCl₃ on melting because of a significant drop in the CN. The same authors subsequently determined⁹³ the total $F(Q)$ of

molten LaX₃ and CeX₃ (X = Cl, Br, I) systems by ND. This time, they employed the difference techniques of ND by assuming that LaX₃ and CeX₃ melts for a given halide ion are isomorphic (see earlier subsection "Neutrons"). The results now show the nearest-neighbour, La-Cl distance and the CN, $\bar{n}_{\text{La}}^{\text{Cl}}$ to be 2.93 Å and 8.2 as compared to the previous values of 2.88 Å and 6.4, respectively. It is important to note here that it is sometimes difficult⁶⁻⁸ to derive quantitative structural information from the total $F(Q)$ for 3 : 1 halide melts. This is especially true when there are overlapping contributions to a given peak in the total $G(r)$. It appears, therefore, that the structural parameters derived from the isomorphic substitution technique are more accurate because firstly, the two difference functions are heavily weighted, in M-Cl and Cl-Cl correlations, respectively, and secondly, they do not contain significant contributions from the other pairs. The simulated results from a separate MD study performed on LaCl₃ and CeCl₃ using the PIM show¹¹⁸ reasonably good agreement not only with the experimental total $F(Q)$, but also with the isomorphic difference functions obtained from the above ND studies.

The local structure of LaCl₃ has been investigated¹²¹ by XAFS using the La K-edge in both the solid and molten states. The results show that the nearest-neighbour La-Cl distance decreases from 2.94 Å in the solid to 2.89 Å ($\bar{n}_{\text{La}}^{\text{Cl}} = 7.4$) in the melt. The authors report the nearest La-La distance to be 4.9 Å, and conclude a distorted corner-sharing arrangement between the connected polyhedra. The structures of molten LaCl₃ and LaBr₃ investigated recently by XRD in conjunction with PIM MD simulations show¹²² that 7- and 8-fold coordination geometries, LaCl₇⁴⁻ and LaCl₈⁵⁻, are predominantly present in the melt, and that LaBr₃ is isomorphous to LaCl₃.

The short-range structures of LaCl₃ and LaCl₃ + Li₂O¹²³ systems have been investigated recently by XAFS using the La K-edge at a number of temperatures from RT until 1173 K/1223 K. XAFS measurements¹²⁴ on a number of lanthanide fluoride-alkali metal fluoride systems, 0.2 LnF₃-0.8 MF (Ln = La, Ce, Nd, Sm, and M = Li, Na, K) carried out recently at 300 and 1173 K reveal that the nearest-neighbour Ln³⁺-F⁻ distances and the corresponding CNs of F⁻ around Ln³⁺ in the molten state ($r_{\text{La-F}} = 2.42-2.43$ Å, $N_{\text{La-F}} = 5.7-6.7$; $r_{\text{Ce-F}} = 2.42$ Å, $N_{\text{Ce-F}} = 5.9-6.9$; $r_{\text{Nd-F}} = 2.39-2.40$ Å, $N_{\text{Nd-F}} = 6.7-6.9$; $r_{\text{Sm-F}} = 2.35$ Å, $N_{\text{Sm-F}} = 3.9-4.6$) depend mainly on the lanthanide ion rather than the alkali metal ion. It is suggested that while the LaF₃, CeF₃, and NdF₃ systems are 6-fold coordinated, SmF₃ is 4-fold coordinated, and this is in accord with the structural differences

in their crystalline phases (LaF_3 , CeF_3 , NdF_3 : tysonite, and SmF_3 : orthorhombic). LaF_3 -LiF and YF_3 -LiF molten systems have also been investigated¹²⁵ recently by EXAFS at the La and Y L_{III} -edges, and NMR spectroscopy. Local structures of six rare earth fluorides, LnF_3 ($\text{Ln} = \text{Gd}, \text{Dy}, \text{Ho}, \text{Er}, \text{Yb}, \text{Lu}$) in both the solid and molten states have been investigated¹²⁶ recently by XAFS at the Ln- L_{III} absorption edge. The results in the molten state reveal that, on average, 6-7 coordinated polyhedra are formed in their 1st coordination shells, and the nearest-neighbour $\text{Ln}_3^+ \text{-F}^-$ distances of 2.28, 2.24, 2.23, 2.21, 2.20, 2.19 Å, respectively, in GdF_3 , DyF_3 , HoF_3 , ErF_3 , YbF_3 , LuF_3 , are almost similar to the sum of their ionic radii.

The ND results on the MX_3 ($\text{M} = \text{La}, \text{Ce}$ and $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$) melts show⁹³ that the FSDP in the total structure factor, $F(Q)$, arising from the cation correlations, moves to lower Q -values (1.12 Å⁻¹ for La/CeCl_3 ; 0.93/0.88 Å⁻¹ for La/CeBr_3 and 0.81/0.77 Å⁻¹ for La/CeI_3) with increase in the anion size. This shift to lower Q -values is probably indicative of enhanced separation in real space of the cation-centred polyhedra. A similar shift in the positions of the prepeaks to lower Q -values with increase in the anion size from Cl^- (1.81 Å) to Br^- (1.96 Å) to I^- (2.20 Å) has also been observed in the three zinc and nickel halides (see previous section "molten divalent-metal halides (MX_2) and their mixtures"). The CNs, \bar{n}_M^X decrease from 9 for MCl_3 and MBr_3 , which melt from UCl_3 -type structure to 8.2 and 7.4, respectively, and from 8 for MI_3 , melting from PuBr_3 -type structure to 6.7. The CNs in the three systems, thus, do not appear to change substantially on melting. The XRD results of molten LaBr_3 , predicting¹¹⁶ octahedral coordination ($\bar{n}_{\text{La}}^{\text{Br}} = 6$) are in contradiction not only with the above ND results ($\bar{n}_{\text{La}}^{\text{Br}} = 7.4$), but also with the results ($\bar{n}_{\text{La}}^{\text{Br}} = 7.1$) from a separate MD simulation study¹²⁷.

ND measurements on molten UCl_3 carried out in conjunction with the RIM and PIM MD simulations show^{91,107,108} that the U^{3+} ion is coordinated to ~7 chloride ions, suggesting a polyhedral arrangement with a nearest-neighbour U-Cl distance of 2.82 Å. These results are in disagreement with those obtained from earlier XRD and MD work¹¹⁵, where the structure of UCl_3 is proposed to be octahedral. Recently, however, the same X-ray results have been reanalyzed¹²⁸ without the use of any damping factor (or a window function) and in conjunction with the PIM MD simulations. The newly reported values from these studies, $r(\text{U}^{3+} \text{-Cl}^-) = 2.85$ Å and $\text{CN} = 8$, suggest the existence of predominantly

$(\text{UCl}_8)^{5-}$ species in the melt. It is also suggested that the U-Cl $\text{CN} = 8$ is slightly overestimated due to contribution from the $\text{Cl}^- \text{-Cl}^-$ correlation to the first peak that corresponds to the U-Cl correlation, in the total $G(r)$. There appears to be nothing wrong with the previously collected experimental XRD data¹¹⁵ on UCl_3 or any of a number of other MX_3 melts reported^{57,116} earlier. Nevertheless, it is probable that during the data analysis stage some sorts of window functions were used for Fourier transformation of the XRD structure factor data in order to get smooth and presentable $G(r)$. Although this procedure of using window functions may not produce any shift in the positions of the peaks in the smoothed $G(r)$ functions, it is most likely to cause a severe reduction in the CNs. This has been confirmed now by the revisited XRD data on UCl_3 (see the above discussion). Other methods of inverting the experimental scattering functions, such as the minimum noise reconstruction technique¹²⁹⁻¹³¹ and the maximum entropy methods¹³² have been proposed and widely used. These are particularly well suited for transforming noisy signals. In the molten state, UCl_3 is structurally isomorphic to LaCl_3 , both showing similar features in their ND total structure factors, $F(Q)$. This is consistent with the fact that both compounds (see Table 5) melt from UCl_3 -type crystal structure with similar melting points and similar values of the cationic radii, La^{3+} (1.032 Å) and U^{3+} (1.025 Å). The $F(Q)$ of molten UCl_3 from ND shows a FSDP at 1.1 Å⁻¹ arising from intermediate-range correlations, and reflecting strong local structures linked by some form of connectivity between the local coordination polyhedra.

A comparison reveals that while the cation in molten DyCl_3 is 6-fold coordinate, that in UCl_3 is 7-fold coordinate. The first peak in $g_{\text{Dy-Cl}}(r)$ yields a CN of 6, and the Cl-Dy-Cl bond angle distribution and the Cl-Cl separation distance are also consistent with the octahedral coordination in molten DyCl_3 . For UCl_3 however, the Cl-Cl distance is found to be far less. The next peak in $g_{\text{Cl-Cl}}(r)$ reflecting the correlations across the first coordination shell has a larger area in UCl_3 than in DyCl_3 , which is again consistent with a higher CN in UCl_3 . Similar behaviour has been observed in molten LaCl_3 . These results clearly indicate that while the octahedral (6-fold) coordination in DyCl_3 is preserved on melting, the CN in UCl_3 decreases from 9 in the crystal to 7 in the melt. Also, the depth of the first minimum in $g_{\text{M-Cl}}(r)$ increases with the decrease in cation size from UCl_3 to DyCl_3 , indicating (see Fig. 10) that with the decrease in cation size the first coordination shell becomes more tightly bound and, it is less likely to exchange anions with the bulk.

Integration of the first peak to this first minimum gives a CN of 7.05 for UCl_3 and 5.99 for DyCl_3 . These results suggest that with decrease in the cation radius from UCl_3 (or LaCl_3) to DyCl_3 , (i) the octahedral coordination becomes progressively more stable and, (ii) the ionic conductivity should decrease gradually, as has been observed.

Fig. 10. The partial PDFs, $g_{\alpha\beta}(r)$ of molten UCl_3 (lines and points) and DyCl_3 (lines). The main peak in $g_{\text{MM}}(r)$ is a doublet. It becomes well resolved with decreasing cation size from UCl_3 to DyCl_3 . The low- r feature is associated with a pair of cations connected to each other via a pair of chloride ions, while the large- r feature with a pair of cations sharing a single anion (Cl^-). Shift of the first feature to substantially smaller separations is caused due to the two cations being drawn together by the edge-sharing arrangement.

The results also highlight the fact that polarisation effects are not so significant (see Fig. 11) in molten UCl_3 as in DyCl_3 , due probably to the greater ionicity of the bond in UCl_3 . While the elimination of polarisation effects in molten DyCl_3 removes the edge-sharing configurations and moves the apex-sharing configurations to larger r , this effect is substantially subdued in the case of molten UCl_3 (see Fig. 11). This is understandable since the cation size in UCl_3 being larger, the polarising power of U^{3+} is much less than that of Dy^{3+} in DyCl_3 , and according to Fajans' rules the more the polarising power of a cation the greater is the degree of covalent character in the ionic bond. The PIM MD simulations on molten LaCl_3 also show¹¹⁸ that the polarization effects in it (similar to those in UCl_3) are weaker than those in YCl_3 (isomorphic to DyCl_3) because of the larger cation radius. This indicates that the structures in LaCl_3 and UCl_3 melts are more dominated by the Coulomb repulsion effects. From this point of view, both LaCl_3 and UCl_3 appear to be closer to the classical ionic model.

Fig. 11. The M-Cl-M bond angle distributions in molten UCl_3 and DyCl_3 . The larger angle features due to corner-sharing octahedra dominate the RIM, and the smaller angle features due to edge-sharing octahedra dominate the PIM MD simulations.

ND measurements on $\text{UCl}_3 + \text{MCl}$ ($\text{M} = \text{Li}, \text{Na}, \text{K}, \text{Cs}$) mixed melts at different compositions have been reported^{107,108}. A FSDP appears in the total structure factors, $F(Q)$, of all these systems. This pre-peak decreases and shifts to smaller Q -value with increase in the concentration of ${}^0\text{LiCl}$, suggesting a gradual loosening and final break-up of the polyhedral network in pure UCl_3 . The effect of adding increasing amounts of ${}^0\text{LiCl}$, ${}^0\text{Li}$ being a null scatterer, is to make available additional halide ions to the polyvalent metal ion, U^{3+} . The pre-peak increases and moves to smaller Q -values with increase in size of the alkali metal ion in the order $\text{Li} < \text{Na} < \text{K} < \text{Cs}$. Further analysis of the ND data, and MD simulations using RIM/PIM on these $(\text{UCl}_3)_x(\text{MCl})_{(1-x)}$ melts are in progress and will be reported separately.

NdCl_3 also crystallises in the UCl_3 -type structure (see Table 5). ND data at the total structure function level have been used¹⁰⁶ in conjunction with the XRD data from a separate study^{57,112} to obtain a model structure using

the Reverse Monte Carlo (RMC) modelling. The results, however, did not provide structural details of much significance. Nevertheless, from the similarity of the RMC generated triplet correlation functions for the liquid with those in the crystalline state, it is suggested that the local structure in the melt although considerably more disordered, still retains some characteristics of the solid phase. The presence of a FSDP in the total $F(Q)$ at $\sim 1 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ indicates the existence of IRO in this melt.

The EXAFS spectra of NdCl_3 and DyCl_3 at the Nd and Dy L_{III} -absorption edges (see Table 3) over a range of temperatures have been obtained^{133,134} in both the solid and liquid phases (see Fig. 12). The results show that (i) both compounds undergo structural changes on melting and the effect is larger in NdCl_3 , (ii) the type of phase transition on melting of the two compounds is different, and (iii) NdCl_3 shows a solid-solid structural phase transition, which is absent in DyCl_3 . XAFS measurements¹³⁵ on NdCl_3 and CeCl_3 carried out at the K-absorption edges of Nd and Ce reveal the nearest-neighbour $\text{Ln}^{3+}-\text{Cl}^-$ distances and corresponding CNs of Cl^- around Ln^{3+} to be 2.73 Å, 6.96, and 2.81 Å, 6.52, respectively, suggesting thereby, that both Ce and Nd are surrounded by more than 6 chlorides.

DyCl_3 transforms into AlCl_3 structure before melting where it is structurally isomorphous to YCl_3 and melts with similarly low values of ΔS_m and $\Delta V/V_1$ (see Table 5). The ionic sizes of Y^{3+} and Dy^{3+} are also similar. From the proximity of Dy to Y in Pettifor's chemical scale, it has been suggested⁹⁵ that DyCl_3 should show similar melting mechanism and liquid structure as YCl_3 . The structural results from the NDIS and MD studies on DyCl_3 have already been discussed earlier in this section.

YCl_3 and AlCl_3 , however, show entirely different melting mechanisms, with very different values for their melting and transport properties. Earlier ND results^{95,96} for molten YCl_3 show (i) a FSDP at $Q \approx 0.95 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ associated with IRO in the melt, and (ii) the values of distances and CNs obtained by Gaussian fitting of the peaks in the $G(r)$ as $r_{\text{Y-Cl}} = 2.71 \text{ \AA}$, $\bar{n}_{\text{Y}}^{\text{Cl}} = 5.9$ and $\bar{n}_{\text{Cl}}^{\text{Cl}} = 8$ to 9, confirming an octahedral coordination for Y. The liquid structure calculations¹³⁶ for an ionic model of molten YCl_3 indicate that it melts into a loose ionic network structure formed by edge-sharing octahedra. The distances and CNs, $r_{\text{Y-Cl}} = 2.72 \text{ \AA}$, $\bar{n}_{\text{Y}}^{\text{Cl}} = 5.7$, $r_{\text{Cl-Cl}} = 3.55 \text{ \AA}$ and $\bar{n}_{\text{Cl}}^{\text{Cl}} = 7.8$, also obtained by the Gaussian fitting procedure on the total $G(r)$ in a recent ND study⁹⁴ are in agreement with the earlier values^{95,96}. The PIM MD simulation results¹¹⁸ on molten YCl_3 show a substantial dis-

Fig. 12. The EXAFS signals of (a) NdCl_3 in the solid (293 K) and liquid (1073 K) phases, (b) DyCl_3 in the solid (293 K) and liquid (1036 K) phases, (c) the radial structure functions of NdCl_3 at 293 K : —, NdCl_3 at 1073 K : ooo, DyCl_3 at 293 K : ---, and DyCl_3 at 1036 K : •••. Adopted from Refs. 133,134.

agreement between the simulated and either of the above two experimental ND $F(Q)$ almost over the entire range from $\sim 2-8 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$. To what extent these discrepancies in the total $F(Q)$ are due to strong cancellation effects between contributing PSFs could not be ascertained¹¹⁸. It is worth noting that the same PIM simulations reproduced the behaviour of molten DyCl_3 at the PSF level very well (see earlier discussion), and the two systems, DyCl_3 and YCl_3 , are believed to be isomorphous. It may be that these

discrepancies have exposed the limitations of the "generic" nature of the PIM.

XAFS measurements on YCl_3 using the Y K-edge (see Table 3) show¹³⁷ that the nearest-neighbour Y-Cl distance increases from 2.65 Å in the solid to 2.72 Å ($\bar{n}_{\text{Y}^{\text{Cl}}} = 6$) in the melt that has an edge-sharing octahedral network structure, in agreement with the earlier results from other studies. The results show that the 6-fold coordination in molten YCl_3 gets stabilized on the addition of alkali metal chlorides (LiCl-KCl eutectic). It is also suggested¹³⁷ from XAFS studies using the Br K-edge that the bridging through a Br^- between YBr_6^{3-} units breaks to form free and stable octahedral units in LiBr rich melts with YBr_3 .

The total structure factors, $F(Q)$ of molten TbCl_3 , HoCl_3 , and ErCl_3 determined by ND⁹⁴ show a FSDP indicative of IRO, and its position shifts to smaller Q -values from 1.01 Å⁻¹ (TbCl_3) → 0.95 Å⁻¹ (HoCl_3) → 0.92 Å⁻¹ (ErCl_3) with a decrease in size 0.92 → 0.90 → 0.89 Å of the cation. The first and second peaks in the total $G(r)$ show a significant overlap, and the peaks are broadened due to the limited Q -range ($\cong 10$ Å⁻¹) of the three sets of data. The two peaks in real space were fitted to a sum of Gaussians, and the distances and CNs are reported as : $r_{\text{M-Cl}}$ ($\bar{n}_{\text{M}^{\text{Cl}}}$) = 2.72 Å (6.3), 2.76 Å (6.4), 2.74 Å (5.6), and $r_{\text{Cl-Cl}}$ ($\bar{n}_{\text{Cl}^{\text{Cl}}}$) = 3.58 Å (8.1), 3.59 Å (8.1) and 3.58 Å (8.9), respectively for TbCl_3 , HoCl_3 and ErCl_3 . The CNs (≈ 6) in the molten state are in accord with the octahedral coordination of the cations in the high-temperature crystal phases (Table 5) of the three compounds. The ratios, r_{-}/r_{+-} for the three melts and also for the YCl_3 , discussed before, fall in the range 1.30–1.34, suggesting a distortion of MCl_6^{3-} from regular (expected value ~ 1.41) octahedral geometry. The octahedral coordination in these compounds, similar to that in YCl_3 and DyCl_3 , is thus preserved on melting, which is consistent with a small $\Delta V/V_1$ observed for all of them. It is not surprising because all the five cations (Tb^{3+} , Ho^{3+} , Er^{3+} , Y^{3+} , Dy^{3+}) have similar values of ionic radii in the range 0.90–0.92 Å.

The total structure factor of molten TbCl_3 re-determined by performing ND measurement¹³⁸ over a relatively extended Q -space as compared to the previous ND studies (Q -range $\cong 10$ Å⁻¹, see above) improves resolution of the data in real space, as expected. Inquisitively, the new experimental results are found to be significantly different from those obtained from PIM MD simulations in which the interaction potential parameters were optimised for TbCl_3 to enhance agreement with the pre-

vious ND data⁹⁴ over a limited Q -range. This further exposes the limitations of the "generic" nature of the PIM (see earlier discussion on YCl_3) and highlights the need for further development/improvement of this model not only for TbCl_3 , but also for other MX_3 systems with wide ratios of ion-sizes.

In comparison to the above ND results, the structure of molten ErCl_3 investigated¹¹⁷ by XRD report the Er^{3+} - Cl^- , Cl^- - Cl^- , Er^{3+} - Er^{3+} distances and corresponding CNs as 2.63 Å (5.8), 3.75 Å (8-9) and 4.05 Å (1-2), respectively. The ratio $r_{-}/r_{+-} = 1.43$ is closer to the value 1.41 expected for octahedral geometry. By considering different structural models the authors propose a clustering of distorted octahedra with edge-sharing arrangement ($\text{Er}_2\text{Cl}_{10}^{4-}$), and also the formation of a small amount of $\text{Er}_2\text{Cl}_{11}^{5-}$ (corner-sharing octahedra) ions in the melt. XRD results¹³⁹ on $(\text{ErCl}_3)_{0.25}(\text{NaCl})_{0.75}$ and $(\text{ErCl}_3)_{0.25}(\text{KCl})_{0.75}$ mixed melts, analysed by a least-squares model fitting of the experimental total $F(Q)$, show the nearest-neighbour distances and CNs for the Er^{3+} - Cl^- , Cl^- - Cl^- , Er^{3+} - Er^{3+} correlations as 2.61 Å (5.67), 3.90 Å (9.49), 5.15 Å (4.25), and 2.65 Å (5.73), 3.89 Å (8.93), 5.17 Å (4.10), respectively for the ErNa_3Cl_6 and ErK_3Cl_6 melts. Since the Er^{3+} - Er^{3+} distance of 5.15 and 5.17 Å in the two mixed melts is much longer than 4.05 Å in pure ErCl_3 melt, it is proposed that the edge- $(\text{Er}_2\text{Cl}_{10}^{4-})$ and corner-shared $(\text{Er}_2\text{Cl}_{11}^{5-})$ clustering of distorted octahedra observed in pure ErCl_3 is broken into discrete octahedra of the type ErCl_6^{3-} by the addition of alkali metal chlorides.

The total ND structure factors, $F(Q)$, of molten DyBr_3 , YBr_3 , HoBr_3 and ErBr_3 show^{98,110} the presence of a FSDP at 0.87 (2), 0.82 (2), 0.80 (2) and 0.79 (2) Å⁻¹, respectively, indicating the presence of IRO in each of these melts, and all of them crystallise into the same hexagonal close-packed FeCl_3 -type structure at room temperature. The results for all the four systems show that on melting, a substantial number of MBr_6^{3-} octahedral units survive but get distorted from regular geometry, and a large number of them are connected by edge-sharing to give IRO of cation correlations. Assuming structural isomorphism between DyBr_3 and YBr_3 , the ND difference technique was also used to analyse the difference functions, and the results show that the M-Br CN does not change significantly from 6 when $(\text{Dy}/\text{Y})\text{Br}_3$ melts and the ratio, $r_{-}/r_{+-} = 1.33$ in the liquid. In comparison, $(\text{La}/\text{Ce})\text{Br}_3$ systems show a reduction in the CN from 9 to 7.4 on melting, and the ratio r_{-}/r_{+-} for them is 1.25 (see previous discussion). Obviously, a decrease in the

cation radius from 1.02 Å for $\text{La}^{3+}/\text{Ce}^{3+}$ to 0.91 Å for $\text{Dy}^{3+}/\text{Y}^{3+}$ leads to an increase in the covalent character, and as a result we expect the polarisation effects in the La/Ce-systems not to be as significant as in the Dy/Y-systems. Similar behaviour was observed in $\text{DyCl}_3/\text{YCl}_3$ vis-a-vis $\text{LaCl}_3/\text{CeCl}_3$ systems (see earlier discussion).

InCl_3 has the AlCl_3 structure in the crystal and its volume change on melting is large (see Table 5). However, both its melting temperature and ionic conductivity are similar to YCl_3 rather than AlCl_3 . The total ND measurements on molten InCl_3 yielded¹⁰⁵ a CN, $\bar{n}_{\text{Ln}}^{\text{Cl}}$, between 5 and 6, and the results suggest a partial survival of the network structure in the melt which is in contrast to the low metal-ion coordination in BiCl_3 (see below). The total ND measurements on bismuth trihalides, BiX_3 ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$), carried out at a number of temperatures reveal¹⁰⁴ that the molten BiX_3 systems behave like molecular liquids similar to PX_3 . A separate ND study on molten BiCl_3 indicates¹⁰⁵ a metal-ion coordination of ~ 3 , and suggests a molecular configuration in the melt similar to the previous results. If monomers are the basic constituents present, they should be strongly interacting to allow relatively fast exchange of the halogen ions in accord with the observed ionic conductivity of the melt, which is appreciable. It has been suggested¹⁰⁵ that the nature of the structure and bonding in InCl_3 and BiCl_3 melts is intermediate between the network structure of YCl_3 and DyCl_3 on one hand, and well defined molecular configurations of AlCl_3 and FeCl_3 (see later discussion) on the other.

The local structures of molten BiCl_3 and its mixtures at different compositions in LiCl-KCl eutectic melt have been investigated¹⁴⁰ recently by XAFS. The results show (i) the molecular nature of pure BiCl_3 melt with a Bi-Cl CN ≈ 3 , which is similar to the earlier findings by ND experiments (see the above discussion), and (ii) drastic changes from molecular to ionic liquid with decreasing concentrations of BiCl_3 in the mixed melts.

The total ND structure factors, $F(Q)$, of both ScCl_3 and ScI_3 melts show⁹⁷ a FSDP at 0.75 \AA^{-1} , which is indicative of the presence of IRO. The first peaks in the $G(r)$ yield values for the Sc-X distances and CNs as 2.48 Å (4.8) in ScCl_3 and 2.76 Å (4.7) in ScI_3 , indicating a reduction in the Sc-X CN from 6 in the solid to ~ 5 in both the melts. Also, the first peaks in the $G(r)$ do not return to their $G(0)$ limits on the high- r sides, and this suggests a significant mobility of the ions from and to the first coordination shells, in agreement with the observed high electrical conductivity. It is proposed that ScCl_3 ,

similar to InCl_3 and BiCl_3 (discussed above), may also have characteristics that are intermediate between $\text{YCl}_3/\text{DyCl}_3$ and $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{FeCl}_3$.

The total ND results of molten AlCl_3 have been analysed⁹⁹ by RMC modelling. The experimental $G(r)$ show a clear first deep minimum (unlike that in ScCl_3 or ScI_3) after the well-resolved Al-Cl principal peak at 2.11 Å, indicating little movement of anions into and out of the first coordination shell. The CN, $\bar{n}_{\text{Al}}^{\text{Cl}} = 4$, and the ratio, $r_-/r_+ = 1.66$ suggest a regular four-fold tetrahedral geometry in molten AlCl_3 . The PIM simulation results¹¹⁹ show that an overwhelming majority of the four-fold coordinate Al^{3+} ions are involved in dimers. The structural results of molten AlBr_3 , GaBr_3 and GaI_3 by ND also show¹⁰⁹ the existence of dimeric M_2X_6 units associated with tetrahedral coordination. The melting of AlCl_3 from an ionic layer-structure into a molecular liquid of Al_2Cl_6 units is accompanied by low melting point, very large values of ΔS_m and $\Delta V/V_1$. The large increase in volume and entropy on melting is explained in terms of the change in the CN of Al^{3+} from 6 in the crystal to 4 in the melt. In crystalline AlBr_3 , however, the tetrahedral coordination of Al^{3+} ions in the crystal lattice of molecular Al_2Br_6 dimers is retained in the melt, and this is consistent with the fact that the observed ΔS_m and $\Delta V/V_1$ values in AlBr_3 are less than half of those observed in AlCl_3 (see Table 5).

The diffraction patterns of $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{LiCl}$, $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{NaCl}$, and AlX_3/KX ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$) mixed melts^{99,141,142}, all exhibit a FSDP indicative of IRO. The NDIS measurements on $(\text{AlCl}_3)_{0.5}(\text{LiCl})_{0.5}$ melt have been used to derive the PDFs, $g_{\text{AlCl}}(r)$, $g_{\text{AlAl}}(r)$, and $g_{\text{ClCl}}(r)$, and the results¹⁴¹ indicate a tetrahedral distribution of Cl^- ions around Al^{3+} with the existence of well defined AlCl_4^- tetrahedra in the mixed melt. The structureless form of $g_{\text{AlAl}}(r)$ suggests very little Al-Cl-Al bridging between these tetrahedra. The results from total ND measurements on $\text{AlCl}_3 + \text{LiCl}$ and $\text{AlCl}_3 + \text{NaCl}$ covering the entire composition range suggest⁹⁹ that connectivity through chains of corner-linked tetrahedral units formed by Al-Cl-Al bridges is proportionately reduced, as expected, upon the addition of alkali metal halide. The results from total ND studies on mixed melts, $(\text{AlX}_3)_{0.67}(\text{KX})_{0.33}$ and $(\text{AlX}_3)_{0.75}(\text{KX})_{0.25}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}$ and Br), imply¹⁴² a tetrahedral coordination of X atoms around each Al, but the authors do not preclude the existence of other structural units in the melts. In fact, model calculations based on random packing of structural units reveal the presence of Al_2X_7^- and $\text{Al}_3\text{X}_{10}^-$ anionic species in the mixed melts.

The structural results from XRD on mixed halide melts, such as $(\text{AlCl}_3)_{0.5}(\text{LiCl})_{0.5}$, $(\text{AlCl}_3)_x(\text{NaCl})_{(1-x)}$ ($x = 0.5, 0.55, 0.6, 0.7$), and $(\text{AlCl}_3)_x(\text{BPC})_{(1-x)}$ ($x = 0.5, 0.67$), where BPC = n-butyl pyridinium chloride, have been compiled and discussed⁵⁷.

ND measurements on molten FeCl_3 combined with model calculations and computer simulations indicate^{102,103} that melting is accompanied by a change in the local structure from an octahedral environment of the Fe^{3+} ions in the crystal to a tetrahedral environment in the liquid in which Fe_2Cl_6 molecular units exhibit substantial intermolecular correlations. This behaviour is similar to that observed in AlCl_3 but in contrast to that in YCl_3 or DyCl_3 where octahedral coordination of M^{3+} ions is preserved on melting. The PIM simulated results¹¹⁹ also show the cation in molten FeCl_3 to be 4-fold coordinate, and the presence of Fe_2Cl_6 dimers.

A combined ND and XRD analyses of SbCl_3 showed^{100,101} that the liquid is structured in monomeric molecular units. The average arrangement of the discrete units is non-random and, with close intermolecular Sb---Cl contacts, results in a well defined distribution centred ~ 3.4 Å, a distance much shorter than that expected from van der Waals interactions alone. The results suggest a distorted octahedral arrangement of Cl around each Sb, which has 3 Cl neighbours from other molecules at 3.4 Å in addition to the 3 bonded chlorines at 2.35 Å. The structure of the SbCl_3 melt is described in terms of chains of SbCl_3 molecules stacked in "umbrella" configurations with the interaction between pairs of molecules within a given chain to be much stronger than the van der Waals forces, while the interactions between the chains to be much weaker.

Miscellaneous single and mixed melts :

Metal nitrates :

Molten nitrates have relatively low melting points. They provide industrially important low temperature baths and show superior glass forming capabilities owing to the tendency of the nitrate ion to resist reorientation in the disordered phase. They exhibit rich phase behaviour on mixing with other nitrates and are essential ingredients in many industrial fertilizers and explosives. The structural results on several single and mixed molten nitrate systems, such as LiNO_3 ^{143,144}, NH_4NO_3 ¹⁴⁵, and $\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3\text{-Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ ¹⁴⁶ by the NDIS technique, and MNO_3 ($\text{M} = \text{Li, Na, K, Rb, Cs, Ag, and Tl}$) and $\text{LiNO}_3\text{-RbNO}_3$ by the ND technique have been reported¹⁴⁷⁻¹⁴⁹. As an illustration, we discuss here the results of molten LiNO_3 in which isotopic substitution on Li- and N- nuclei have

been used to determine the ion-ion and ion-counterion partial structure factors, PSFs, relating¹⁴³ to the $g_{\text{Li-Li}}(r)$, $g_{\text{Li-N}}(r)$, and $g_{\text{Li-O}}(r)$ PDFs (shown in Fig. 13) by using the nuclear reactor source at the ILL, Grenoble (France), and those relating¹⁴⁴ to the $g_{\text{Li-N}}(r)$, $g_{\text{Li-O}}(r)$, $g_{\text{N-N}}(r)$, $g_{\text{N-O}}(r)$, and $g_{\text{O-O}}(r)$ PDFs by using the time-of-flight (TOF) ND measurements on a spallation source at KENS, Tsukuba (Japan). The results reveal that a central Li^+ is surrounded on an average by about four nearest-neighbouring NO_3^- ions, one oxygen in each of these nitrate ions facing towards Li^+ , with the nearest-neighbour distances, $r_{\text{Li-O}} = 2.1$ Å, $r_{\text{Li-N}} = 2.8$ Å, $r_{\text{Li-Li}} = 4.1$ Å, and $r_{\text{N-N}} = 4.8$ Å. The space- and time-averaged local structure in the molten state is found to be appreciably different from that in the crystalline state. The discrepancies between these results and those reported by MD com-

Fig. 13. The PDFs¹⁴³ (a) $g_{\text{Li-N}}(r)$, $g_{\text{Li-O}}(r)$, and (b) $g_{\text{Li-Li}}(r)$ in molten LiNO_3 compared with $g_{\text{N-N}}(r)$ ¹⁴⁴ in inset; after Adaya *et al.*¹⁴³.

puter simulations. where the reported nearest-neighbour Li-O and Li-Li distances of 1.86 Å and 3.86 Å and the corresponding coordination numbers are far less, highlight the uncertainties in the effective pair potentials used in the MD study¹⁴⁷.

XRD results on molten metal nitrates of Li, Na, K, Rb, Cs and Ag have been compiled⁵⁷. The structures are also reported¹⁵⁰ on molten systems of the type (Ag, K, Na)-(I, NO₃), including mixed cation systems such as AgNO₃-KNO₃ and mixed anion systems such as AgI-AgNO₃, at different compositions. The structures of molten NaNO₂, NaNO₃, and NaNO₃-NaNO₂ eutectic have been investigated¹⁵¹ by XRD and MD.

Other single and mixed melts :

Total ND and XRD measurements on molten Li₂CO₃ have been analysed¹⁵² by RMC modeling to generate a 3-D structural model of the melt, and the calculated PDFs are found to be different from an earlier MD simulation. However, the CNs, $N_{\text{Li-C}} = 3.8$, $N_{\text{O-Li}} = 2.4$, and $N_{\text{Li-O}} = 3.7$ are in agreement with those obtained from XRD studies. The short-range structures of NaClO₃ and KClO₃ melts have been reported¹⁵³ by ND in conjunction with other techniques.

The structural results from XRD on a variety of other single and mixed melts such as, metal sulfates : Li₂SO₄, Na₂SO₄, K₂SO₄, Cs₂SO₄, Ag₂SO₄, (Li₂SO₄)_x(Na₂SO₄)_(1-x) ($x = 0.75, 0.5, 0.25$), hydrogen sulfates : NaHSO₄, KHSO₄, and NH₄HSO₄, carbonates : Li₂CO₃, Na₂CO₃, K₂CO₃, (Li₂CO₃)_{0.5}(Na₂CO₃)_{0.5}, (Li₂CO₃)_{0.5}(K₂CO₃)_{0.5}, (Na₂CO₃)_{0.5}(K₂CO₃)_{0.5}, (Li₂CO₃)_{0.43}(Na₂CO₃)_{0.32}(K₂CO₃)_{0.25}, tungstates : Na₂WO₄, Na₂W₂O₇, thiocyanates : NaSCN, KSCN, CaSCN, silicates : MgSiO₃, CaSiO₃, and oxides : V₂O₅, B₂O₃, (PbO)_{0.8}(B₂O₃)_{0.2} (in melt and glass), (PbO)_x(SiO₂)_(1-x) ($x = 0.67, 0.5, 0.33$, glass), (PbO)_x(SiO₂)_(1-x) ($x = 0.6512, 0.5036, 0.3378$ - in both melt and glass), (PbO)_{0.5}(GeO₂)_{0.5} (in both melt and glass), SiO₂, (M₂O)_x(SiO₂)_(1-x) ($M = \text{Li, Na, K, and } x = 0.0-0.6$), GeO₂ and Al₂O₃ have been compiled⁵⁷. The structures of M₂O-B₂O₃ ($M = \text{Na, K}$) melts and glasses by ND have been reported¹⁵⁴. From an XAFS investigation¹⁵⁵ at the Zr K-edge of ZrCl₄ in LiCl-KCl eutectic melt, the Zr⁴⁺-Cl⁻ distance and CN are found to be 2.51 Å and 5.9, respectively, suggesting that ZrCl₆²⁻ are the predominant species present in the melt.

Molten metal oxides by levitation techniques :

There has recently been much interest in exploring the use of levitation techniques to examine the structure by ND and XRD of molten salts such as metal oxides,

which are very reactive and high melting ($T_m > 2000$ K). Such container less scattering precludes the possibility of chemical contamination by the container material used in furnace experiments. However, the technique presents major challenge for a neutron or X-ray diffraction experiment because the maximum amount of material, usually ~20-50 mg, that can be supported by a levitator is only 1/20th-1/100th of the material conventionally used in a diffraction experiment on a liquid.

The use of aerodynamic levitation in association with CO₂ laser heating to look at the structure of molten Al₂O₃ (alumina) and Y₂O₃ (yttria) by XRD on a synchrotron radiation source has been demonstrated^{156,157}. The results show the existence of AlO₄⁵⁻ tetrahedral units in which Al atoms are predominantly four-fold coordinated with an average value of the Al-O CN to be 4.4. In contrast to drastic changes in Al₂O₃ on melting, no major structural rearrangements or changes in the cation coordination occur on melting Y₂O₃. This difference in behaviour of change in the coordination upon melting between Al₂O₃ and Y₂O₃ clearly mirrors the difference observed previously between AlCl₃ (or FeCl₃) and YCl₃ (or DyCl₃) (see earlier discussion on MX₃ melts in section "molten trivalent-metal halides (MX₃) and their mixtures"). A ND study on molten Al₂O₃ carried out at ISIS, Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL), UK, using the levitation technique has been reported¹⁵⁸. The data have been interpreted by using a simulation in which model ensembles of Al and O ions were set up to best reproduce the experimental ND structure factor, $F(Q)$. The calculated site-site RDFs and the average value for the Al-O CN of 4.5 in this simulation are found to be consistent with the earlier X-ray data^{156,157}. However, the simulated results reveal the presence of significant numbers of 5- and 6-fold coordinated Al in the melt. The authors, thus, stress that molten alumina certainly cannot be described simply as a predominantly 'tetrahedral liquid', and that the true picture of Al₂O₃ should be taken as one where the octahedral coordination in the solid becomes highly defective on melting.

A review¹⁵⁹ summarizing the results from XRD on levitated liquids in both the supercooled and normal states of several high-temperature molten oxides and other materials has been published in 2000. A new determination¹⁶⁰ of the structure of liquid Al₂O₃, aerodynamically lifted and laser-heated over a wide temperature range that included both the supercooled and normal liquid states, has been made by using synchrotron XRD. No structural differences occur on changing the Ar (reducing) to oxy-

gen (oxidizing) atmospheres. An electrostatic levitation furnace has been designed¹⁶¹ for container less ND work on condensed matter.

Room temperature molten salts and their mixtures :

RTMS are currently attracting great interest as "green solvents" for catalysis and low temperature synthetic chemical purposes, and as electrolytes in energy technology field for electrochemical energy storage (primary batteries) and generation (e.g. fuel cells and photovoltaic devices). They consist of ions and retain many of the benefits of high temperature ionic liquids (HTMS) discussed above, but without the thermal handling problems associated with the HTMS. Their low melting points coupled with the intricate temperature-composition dependence of the physico-chemical properties make these materials as attractive candidates for basic and applied research. Many RTMS are composed of 1,3-dialkylimidazolium, e.g. 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium (EMI^+), or 1,2,3-trialkylimidazolium cations, and chloroaluminate (AlCl_4^-) or perfluorinated anions, e.g. $[\text{BF}_4]^-$, $[\text{PF}_6]^-$, $[\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3]^-$, $[(\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3)_2\text{N}]^-$, $[(\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_2)_3\text{C}]^-$, and $[\text{CF}_3\text{CO}_2]^-$. By changing the alkyl chain on the cation or the anion, a wide variation in their properties can be obtained. As mentioned earlier in this article, although numerous studies concerning their synthesis, physical and electrochemical properties, and their use as a reaction medium have been reported¹⁶², little is known as yet about their liquid structure.

The author of this article is of the view that the problems with the interpretation of structural data on RTMS are somewhat akin to those encountered in molecular liquids¹⁶³⁻¹⁶⁵. Firstly, the basic entities in the RTMS, the molecular cations and anions are not rigid; they have internal vibrations and it is not a trivial problem to characterise them purely in terms of correlations of atomic positions. In reality, severe distortions from arrangements of highest symmetry of atomic positions over and above those arising from internal vibrations may be expected. However, in order to explore the intermolecular structure, the molecular cations and anions will need to be assumed to be almost rigid and their equilibrium geometries estimated, for instance, from the optimisation of geometries of single molecules by *ab initio* molecular orbital calculations (see e.g. Fig. 14) using different basis sets. While such an approach may be adequate for smaller molecules, complications are expected for larger molecular cations and anions. Also, because the largest intra-molecular distances within the molecular cations and anions in RTMS are larger than the shortest interionic

Fig. 14. The equilibrium geometry of 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium (EMI^+) ion optimised by using *ab initio* molecular orbital calculations at the RHF/6-31G* level by the author. The most electronegative elements are the two nitrogen atoms in the imidazolium ring, and the net charge of +1 is distributed throughout the molecular organic ion, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2^+$.

distances, it is not possible to separate the intramolecular and inter-ionic contributions straightforwardly by direct Fourier transformation of the experimental diffraction data.

Secondly, the relative orientations of molecular cations and anions in a RTMS is distinct from their centre-centre separations, and one must take into account the orientational correlations in addition to the correlations between the molecular centres. The problems are further accentuated due to the fact that the scattering pattern consists of an unresolvable sum of several scattering patterns, and that the same type of nucleus is present in more than one position as is usually the case in the RTMS. These difficulties can be partially overcome by the NDIS technique, but in view of the limited number of isotopic substitutions possible in the RTMS its use will be severely restricted. H/D substitution is one possibility for the time being, but the future advancement in technology that may allow the use of $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ isotopic substitution will enable detailed and extensive structural studies to be carried out on a wide range of RTMS. In any circumstance, it is inevitable that one will almost always have to resort to some form of modelling to interpret the structural data on RTMS. Indeed, whatever structural information on RTMS has been derived so far from ND and XRD work is at best semi-quantitative.

A ND study in conjunction with *ab initio* calculations to investigate the structure at room temperature of AlCl_3 -1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride melts at four concentrations (40, 50, 60 and 67 mol% AlCl_3) has been reported¹⁶⁶. *Ab initio* calculations using 6-31G* basis set were performed on the isolated ions (AlCl_4^- , Al_2Cl_7^- , EMI^+) and some of their complexes, such as $\text{AlCl}_4^- \cdots \text{EMI}^+$ and $\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- \cdots \text{EMI}^+$ that are known to form in these melts. The *ab initio* results show no significant

change in the geometry in going from isolated ions AlCl_4^- and EMI^+ to $\text{AlCl}_4^- \cdots \text{EMI}^+$ but do show a change in the Cl-Cl distance in going from Al_2Cl_7^- and EMI^+ to $\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- \cdots \text{EMI}^+$, in reasonable agreement with the ND results.

Another ND structural study on a model ionic liquid 1,3-dimethylimidazolium chloride (m.p. 128°C) by using selective H/D substitution on the imidazolium ion has been reported¹⁶⁷. The Radial Distribution Functions (RDFs) of chloride around imidazolium and imidazolium about imidazolium were obtained from computer simulations of the liquid, in which the forces between atoms and hence their positions were refined continuously to get the best fit between the simulated and the ND data. The results show a significant order within the liquid, and a close relationship observed between the crystal and liquid structures implies that the molecular packing in the first two or three coordination shells is similar in both the phases. The ND data have also been used to derive a structural model using EPSR¹⁶⁸, and the model indicates¹⁶⁹ that the H-bonding interactions between the ring hydrogens and the chloride dominate the structure in both the solid and liquid phases. The structure of liquid 1,3-dimethylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate has been investigated¹⁷⁰ by analyzing the ND data using the EPSR, and compared with the structure of 1,3-dimethylimidazolium chloride. Although the overall structures of the two compounds are found to be similar, significant differences result on varying the anion size.

The structures of a series of 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium fluorohydrogenate (RMIF-2.3 HF, R = alkyl group – M, E, Pr, Bu, Pe, H) RTMS have been investigated^{171,172} by combining the results of XRD on a synchrotron radiation source with the results of *ab initio* molecular orbital calculations carried out at the HF/6-31 G* level. The total structure factors of all these melts show a FSDP at $Q = 1.8 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, and this position is almost at the same distance where a Bragg peak for solid EMIF-HF, indicating a layered structure formed by the molecular cations (EMI^+), is observed. This peak corresponds to interatomic correlations at $\sim 2\pi/Q = 2\pi/1.8 \approx 3.5 \text{ \AA}$. In fact, a broad peak observed in the total $G(r)$ for all these melts at 3.6 \AA is assigned to the intermolecular correlations between the cations. The intramolecular form factors for the various isolated ions, EMI^+ , HF_2^- , H_2F_3^- and H_3F_4^- , were calculated by using the Debye type equation from the structural parameters of equilibrium geometries optimised by the *ab initio* calculations. These were then added in appropriate ratios to calculate the in-

tramolecular form factors for EMI^+ , $\text{EMI}^+ + \text{HF}_2^-$, $\text{EMI}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{F}_3^-$, $\text{EMI}^+ + \text{H}_3\text{F}_4^-$, and $\text{EMI}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{F}_3^- + \text{H}_3\text{F}_4^-$, and the data for each compared with the total experimental XRD structure factor of EMIF-2.3 HF melt. From a much improved agreement between the observed total and calculated intramolecular structure factors at high Q ($> 4 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$) in the case of $\text{EMI}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{F}_3^-$, in which the presence of H_2F_3^- in the melt is taken into consideration, the authors suggest that H_2F_3^- is a major component of the anions in the EMIF-2.3 HF melt. This is so because at high values of the scattering vector, Q , the interionic contribution to the total structure factor is negligible so that the diffraction pattern at high- Q is characteristic of only the intramolecular terms arising from the isolated cations and anions. While it is possible to extract the interionic contribution by subtracting the intramolecular terms from the observed total structure factors and then do further interpretation of the interionic correlations through possibly computer simulations, this does not seem to have been attempted so far.

The structures of 1,3-dimethylimidazolium chloride and hexafluorophosphate salts in both the liquid and solid states have been reported¹⁷³ by using ND and single crystal XRD. A strong correlation between the liquid and crystal structures in both the salts is found. ND in conjunction with EPSR refinement of the data has been used to determine¹⁷⁴ the structures of liquid mixtures of 1,3-dimethylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate with benzene at two concentrations (33 and 67 mol% benzene). Both mixtures show similar structures, however, the ionic liquid structure is significantly altered in the presence of benzene, especially the cation-cation term.

3. Summary and future work

The above discussion on a variety of ionic liquids (belonging to both HTMS and RTMS categories) shows that our knowledge of their structural aspects has greatly improved due to significant advancements made in the experimental ND and XRD techniques. These techniques in conjunction with computer simulations/modeling, *ab initio* molecular orbital calculations, and liquid-state structural theory will continue to play a significant role in deepening our understanding of the ionic liquids. It is anticipated that the neutron and X-ray techniques will continue to be further developed and applied to a wide variety of more complex ionic liquids, such as molten oxides, fluorides, cryolites, room temperature molten salts, and molten salt mixtures of importance in nuclear industry, electrochemical devices, and energy storage systems. It is also clear that the work on the structural aspects of

RTMS is still in its infancy, and we have a long way to go before building the same level of expertise on the structural aspects of RTMS, as we have already built on the HTMS.

Undoubtedly, the well-established difference methods of NDIS remain superior to all other methods for the determination of interatomic pairwise structure. However, it is also vividly clear that no one method will be sufficient to resolve structure at the required level of detail around all the species in a complex ionic liquid. Therefore, studies that combine reference data from AXD or NDIS with extensive EXAFS data are likely to be useful. Also, one must rely on a full complement of diffraction and other techniques including computer simulations and *ab initio* calculations to determine the complete atomic structure of a complex ionic liquid. The new and custom built liquid diffractometers on the second target station at the ISIS, and also on the upcoming DIAMOND synchrotron source being built at the RAL, UK will provide a much needed boost to the ionic liquids community for a wide ranging AXD and EXAFS investigations of these systems, and also for simultaneously probing a broad range of length scales in a variety of scientifically and technologically important complex ionic liquids. This will be particularly important in those cases where different length scale structures of disordered or partially disordered ionic liquids are subtly related to their properties and function. The experimental ND and XRD techniques will also provide exciting new opportunities to resolve the issues of structural frustration that ionic liquids experience on confinement.

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